

D 2.1 Education/ awareness material

Educational materials for fishers' awareness activities (e.g. posters, flyers, and roll-ups) focusing on the problem of marine litter including the role of the fishing industry as polluter; the economic impacts on fisheries; how fishers can minimise waste and reduce harmful environmental impacts (e.g. bycatch, ghost fishing); the potential use of alternative/eco-friendly materials; the strategies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, energy and resource consumption. The educational materials produced target professional fishers using simple, non-scientific language and will be prepared in English, Portuguese, Spanish, Italian and Croatian.

Document Information

Grant Agreement no. 101112812

Call ID	HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01
Project Name	Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating Environmental Impacts of Fishing Gears and Associated Marine Litter
Project Acronym	NETTAG+
Project Website	https://nettagplus.eu/
Deliverable ID	D2.1
Work Package Reference	WP2
Due Date of Deliverable	29/02/2023
Submission Date	29/02/2023
Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Partner	CIIMAR
Participating Partners	APMSHM, ARVI, CoGePa, WWF, MAFA, USC, UAveiro, C&S

Quality information and Revision History

Version	Authors	Date
1	Lisa Sousa, Marisa Almeida, Sandra Ramos	31/01/2024
2	Lisa Sousa, Marisa Almeida, Sandra Ramos	27/02/2024

Summary NETTAG+ Project

NETTAG+ aims to provide a portfolio of three innovative smart and sustainable solutions to address the negative impacts of abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG) on marine life and habitats. NETTAG+ will be based on synergistic activities between the fisheries industry, scientists and NGOs to develop three solutions to PREVENT, AVOID and MITIGATE the harmful impacts of ALDFG.

NETTAG+ will PREVENT marine litter derived from fisheries activities, AVOID loss of fishing gears, and MITIGATE harmful impact by removing existing ALDFG. These three solutions will jointly contribute to reduce ALDFG and marine pollution, namely by: reducing the introduction of hazardous chemicals and microplastics originating from ALDFG; reducing ghost fishing, bycatch and entanglements of sensitive or endangered species on ALDFG; and improving mapping, tracking and recovery technologies to retrieve ALDFG.

NETTAG+ aims to upgrade and upscale the integrative preventive approach that started in the previous NetTag project, and aims to replicate it in Mediterranean regions, providing the fisheries industry with three smart and environmentally-friendly solutions to reduce ALDFG and prevent the environmental impacts of fishing gears. The three solutions will be developed to maturity (TRL 7-8) by the end of the project, and will be tested, validated and demonstrated in real conditions in Atlantic and Mediterranean countries, namely Portugal (PT), United Kingdom (UK), Spain (SP), Italy (IT), Croatia (HR) and Malta (MT). NETTAG+'s ambition is to change the paradigm of the fisheries industry, aspiring to transform the societal perspectives about the role of fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean. NETTAG+ will empower the sector to take effective actions to address marine pollution, promoting their role as key actors to tackle marine pollution.

Contents

Contents	3
Executive Summary	6
1 Introduction	7
2 Educational/awareness materials and actions	9
2.1 General procedures and materials	10
2.2 Workshop #1 - Seminar on marine litter	11
2.2.1 Overview.....	11
2.2.2 Workshop development	11
2.2.3 Resources and materials.....	12
2.3 Workshop #2 - Marine litter produced on board	12
2.3.1 Overview.....	12
2.3.2 Workshop development	13
2.3.3 Resources and materials.....	18
2.4 Workshop #3 - Marine litter collected by fishing gear	19
2.4.1 Overview.....	19
2.4.2 Workshop development	19
2.4.3 Resources and materials.....	24
2.5 Workshop #4 - Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation	24
2.5.1 Overview.....	24
2.5.2 Workshop development	25
2.5.3 Resources and materials.....	29
2.6 Workshop #5 - Reducing fisheries footprint	29
2.6.1 Overview.....	29
2.6.2 Workshop development	30
2.6.3 Resources and materials.....	33
2.7 Workshop #6 - NETTAG+ solutions.....	33
2.7.1 Overview.....	33
2.7.2 Workshop development	34
2.7.3 Resources and materials.....	37
3 Concluding remarks	38
References	39
Annex 1. Participant information sheet	40

Annex 2. Informed consent form	43
Annex 3. Template of the participants list	45
Annex 4. Template of the workshop feedback form	46
Annex 5. Structure of the synthesis report.....	47
Annex 6. NETTAG+ flyer	49
Annex 7. NETTAG+ roll-up banner.....	51
Annex 8. Proposed agenda for Workshop #1	52
Annex 9. NETTAG+ general presentation	53
Annex 10. Seminar on marine litter presentation	56
Annex 11. Proposed agenda for Workshop #2	83
Annex 12. Support material for the Workshop #2.....	84
Annex 13. Exercise sheets for the Workshop #2.....	87
Annex 14. Proposed agenda for Workshop #3	92
Annex 15. Exercise sheets for the Workshop #3.....	93
Annex 16. Proposed agenda for Workshop #4	98
Annex 17. Support material for the Workshop #4.....	99
Annex 18. Exercise sheets for the Workshop #4.....	100
Annex 19. Support material to discuss best practices to reduce bycatch (Workshop #4)	104
Annex 20. Proposed agenda for Workshop #5	109
Annex 21. Support material to discuss the reduction of GHG emissions (Workshop #5)	110
Annex 22. Exercise sheets for the Workshop #5.....	111
Annex 23. Support material to discuss the use of more eco-friendly materials (Workshop #5).....	114
Annex 24. Proposed agenda for Workshop #6	115
Annex 25. Poster for the Workshop #6	116
Annex 26. Exercise sheets for the Workshop #6.....	117

Figures

Figure 1. Illustration of the geographical scope of the NETTAG+ awareness actions	9
Figure 2. Example of the first exercise sheet (workshop #2)	14
Figure 3. Example of the sheet for exercise 2A (workshop #2)	15
Figure 4. Example of the sheet for exercise 2B (workshop #2)	15
Figure 5. Example of the sheet for exercise 3A (workshop #2)	17
Figure 6. Example of the sheet for exercise 3B (workshop #2)	18
Figure 7. Example of the first exercise sheet (workshop #3)	20
Figure 8. Example of the sheet for exercise 2A (workshop #3)	21
Figure 9. Example of the sheet for exercise 2B (workshop #3)	22
Figure 10. Example of the sheet for exercise 3A (workshop #3)	23
Figure 11. Example of the sheet for exercise 3B (workshop #3)	23
Figure 12. Example of the first exercise sheet (workshop #4)	26
Figure 13. Example of the second exercise sheet (workshop #4)	27
Figure 14. Example of the third exercise sheet (workshop #4)	27
Figure 15. Example of the fourth exercise sheet (workshop #4)	28
Figure 16. Example of the first exercise sheet (workshop #5)	31
Figure 17. Example of the second exercise sheet (workshop #5)	31
Figure 18. Example of the third exercise sheet (workshop #5)	32
Figure 19. Example of the poster for the evaluation of the NETTAG+ solutions (workshop #6)	35
Figure 20. Example of the second exercise sheet for PREVENT solutions (workshop #6)	35
Figure 21. Example of the second exercise sheet for AVOID solutions (workshop #6)	36
Figure 22. Example of the second exercise sheet for MITIGATE solutions (workshop #6)	36

Executive Summary

Every year, tons of fishing gear are discarded to the ocean globally, inflicting severe threats to marine habitats and wildlife while causing economic losses to the fishing sector. Addressing marine pollution on a global scale requires cooperation across the science-policy-society interface, combining the know-how of the different actors involved to successfully solve the marine litter global environmental crisis.

This report is an output of 'WP2 - PREVENT: Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean' and delivers the educational materials co-produced by NETTAG+ partners on the issue of marine litter (Task 2.1) to be used in the awareness actions that the NETTAG+ fishers associations and representatives (APMSHM; ARVI; CoGePa; WWF; MAFA) will deliver to their associates (Task 2.2).

The educational materials target professional fishers from different countries, therefore using simple, non-scientific language and will be produced in five languages: English, Portuguese, Spanish, Italian and Croatian.

A package of six workshops was prepared:

- Workshop #1 - Seminar on marine litter
- Workshop #2 - Marine litter produced on board
- Workshop #3 - Marine litter collected by fishing gear
- Workshop #4 - Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation
- Workshop #5 - Reducing fisheries footprint
- Workshop #6 - NETTAG+ solutions

The educational materials will be available on the NETTAG+ project website, so they can be freely used in other projects or initiatives.

Through the development of educational materials and awareness actions, NETTAG+ aims to enhance the comprehension of marine litter issues within professional fishing communities and to foster a transformation in the fisheries industry's perception, shifting from being perceived as a 'polluter' to becoming a 'guardian and cleaner' of the ocean.

Engaging fishers' associations and representatives in the collaborative development of educational materials, as well as their participation in the planning and execution of awareness activities, guarantees that NETTAG+ outputs align with the needs of the fishing community. This approach fosters ownership and enhances the likelihood of influencing behavioural changes.

1 Introduction

Modern fishing gear, predominantly made of non-biodegradable plastic, persist in the environment for extended periods (Brown & Macfadyen, 2007; Iñiguez *et al.*, 2016), causing adverse environmental and socio-economic impacts. This includes adverse effects on biota, water quality, and human health (Drinkwin, 2020). Cooperation across the science-policy-society interface is crucial to address the marine litter global environmental crisis. Fishers, with their local ecological knowledge, contribute significantly to effective marine management decision-making (Freire & García-Allut, 1999; Pita *et al.*, 2020), including identifying fishing grounds and areas with concentrated marine litter. Fishers also play a key role in managing marine litter, by avoiding and retrieving lost fishing gear and by voluntarily collecting and bringing marine litter to local ports for adequate management and recycling.

NETTAG+ is based on collaboration between the fisheries industry, scientists, and NGOs to develop solutions that PREVENT, AVOID, and MITIGATE the harmful impacts of lost fishing gear on marine life and habitats. The actions related with the PREVENT solution are in part focused on the development of educational materials and awareness actions to promote best practices regarding the management of litter, possible use of alternative materials and reduction of emissions and environmental harmful impacts of fishing gear.

The aim of NETTAG+ educational materials and awareness actions is to capitalise on the fishers' willingness to prevent and reduce marine litter derived from fisheries and to help clean the ocean, thus becoming a key player in addressing marine pollution.

With this solution NETTAG+ will tackle several of the specific issues raised during the previous NetTag project, namely:

- Definition of litter (as most fishers did not recognize organic waste as litter, for example), how to properly manage domestic litter on board by fishers, and how to properly manage litter passively collected by nets.
- Urgent need for appropriate facilities at the fishing ports to properly manage litter loaded by fishing vessels for recycling.
- Extent geographic coverage of actions to increase the number of fishers involved and tackle specific local/regional problems.
- Emphasise the role of fishers as guardians and cleaners of the ocean, highlighting the voluntary service they provide when they load the litter that is passively collected by their fishing gear.

This report is an output of 'WP2 - PREVENT: Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean' and delivers the educational materials co-produced by NETTAG+ partners on the issue of marine litter (Task 2.1) to be used in the awareness actions that the NETTAG+ fishers associations and representatives will deliver to their associates (Task 2.2).

The educational materials target professional fishers from different countries, therefore using simple, non-scientific language and will be produced in five languages: English, Portuguese, Spanish, Italian and Croatian. The resources will be available on the project website, so they can be used in other projects or initiatives.

Through the development of educational materials and awareness actions, NETTAG+ aims to enhance the comprehension of marine litter issues within professional fishing communities and to foster a transformation in the fisheries industry's perception, shifting from being perceived as a 'polluter' to becoming a 'guardian and cleaner' of the ocean.

Engaging fishers' associations and representatives in the collaborative development of educational materials, as well as their participation in the planning and execution of awareness activities, guarantees that NETTAG+ outputs align with the needs of the fishing community. This approach fosters ownership and enhances the likelihood of influencing behavioural changes.

2 Educational/awareness materials and actions

A package of six workshops was prepared to raise awareness on the adverse environmental and socio-economic effects of marine litter and abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG), and to identify, promote and implement best practices regarding the management of litter, possible use of alternative materials, emission reduction objectives and reduction of environmental harmful impacts of fishing gear:

- Workshop #1 - Seminar on marine litter
- Workshop #2 - Marine litter produced on board
- Workshop #3 - Marine litter collected by fishing gear
- Workshop #4 - Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation
- Workshop #5 - Reducing fisheries footprint
- Workshop #6 - NETTAG+ solutions

NETTAG+ participatory workshops encompass a broad geographic scope, spanning the North-East Atlantic (Portugal, Spain) and the Mediterranean (Italy, Croatia, Malta). This expansion aims to increase the participation of fishers, targeting a range of 210-350 individuals.

Figure 1. Illustration of the geographical scope of the NETTAG+ awareness actions

NETTAG+ adopts an innovative approach ‘from fishers to fishers’, which consists in involving fishers in initiatives designed by and for their community. This strategy aims to encourage fishers to actively address marine litter, embrace best practices in waste management, and adopt environmentally friendly fishing techniques (e.g. reducing bycatch and consumption of energy/resources). By addressing local constraints and adapting to specific realities, including local fishing activities, this approach ensures relevance and effectiveness.

2.1 General procedures and materials

NETTAG+ partners conducting awareness actions at each venue are responsible for the invitations, managing the registrations and participations, facilitating the sessions, ensuring the signature of consent forms, disseminating the project, and providing a synthesis report. A set of materials, templates and forms have been prepared to support the organisation of workshops and ensure a consistent implementation:

- **NETTAG+ participant information sheet (Annex 1):** providing relevant information about the project, contact details, goals of the engagement activities, and other relevant information. To be handed out to participants, together with the consent form, in the beginning of each event.
- **NETTAG+ informed consent form (Annex 2):** to be signed by each participant in the beginning of each event and stored by partners (each participant should keep a copy for themselves).
- **List of participants template (Annex 3):** to support partners in the registration desk. In the beginning of the event, each participant must sign the participation sheet.
- **Feedback form (Annex 4):** to be distributed to participants in the beginning of the event so they can evaluate it. The forms must be collected by partners in the end of the event.
- **Structure of the synthesis report (Annex 5):** to guide the organising partner in the elaboration of the event synthesis report, which must then be shared with participants.
- **NETTAG+ flyer (Annex 6):** promotional flyer presenting the NETTAG+ project, objectives and expected results to be handed to the participants at the first event.
- **NETTAG+ roll-up banner (Annex 7):** designed for use at internal and external events, namely the participatory workshops, to communicate the project.

These workshops can occur individually or grouped into two or three events, depending on the decision of the responsible partner (fisher's representatives) who organize them, considering the availability of participant fishers and resource management.

2.2 Workshop #1 - Seminar on marine litter

2.2.1 Overview

The first NETTAG+ workshop, entitled 'Seminar on marine litter', is an educational seminar targeting small- and large-scale professional fishers to raise awareness of the problem of marine litter, focusing on the adverse environmental and socio-economic effects of marine litter and ALDFG, how fishers can minimise waste and reduce harmful environmental impacts associated with bycatch and ghost fishing. Moreover, this educational seminar will also address the possible use of alternative materials, and strategies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, energy and resource consumption.

The workshop takes approximately one hour and a half and will address the following themes:

- The importance of the ocean and main threats.
- The problem of marine litter (including plastic and microplastic pollution).
- Contribution of fisheries to marine litter and its adverse environmental and socio-economic impacts (e.g., ALDFG, litter produced on board).
- Other environmental harmful impacts of fisheries (such as bycatch, greenhouse gas emissions).
- European actions to tackle marine litter from sea-based sources.
- Best practices regarding the management of litter, possible use of alternative materials and reduction of emissions and environmental harmful impacts.

The main expected learning outcomes include:

- Understanding marine litter and its effects on marine wildlife, socio-economic activities, and human well-being.
- Gaining insight into other environmental impacts associated with fisheries.
- Introducing participants to best practices to tackle these challenges.

2.2.2 Workshop development

Registration

The registration team welcome the participants and hand them the Participant Information Sheet (Annex 1), two Informed Consent Forms (Annex 2), the NETTAG+ Flyer (Annex 6) and the Feedback form (Annex 4). Participants are asked to sign the presence list and return the signed informed consent form (each participant should keep a copy for themselves).

Welcome and presentation of the NETTAG+ project

| 15 minutes

After the welcome, there will be a quick presentation of the objectives and activities planned for the workshop and a brief presentation of the NETTAG+ project (Annex 9).

Seminar on marine litter

| 60 minutes

The 'Seminar on marine litter' will be presented, using the PowerPoint presentation previously prepared (Annex 10).

Discussion

| 15 minutes

Following the presentation, participants are encouraged to pose questions and engage in a discussion on the seminar topics. Participants are requested to complete the feedback form and to leave it at the registration table.

2.2.3 Resources and materials

Two PowerPoint presentations were prepared, one with a general introduction to the NETTAG+ project (Annex 9) and another one with the themes to be addressed and discussed with fishers during the workshop (Annex 10). Both presentations, prepared in English, are available in the project drive and will be translated to local languages (Portuguese, Spanish, Italian and Croatian). After the awareness actions, the workshop presentations will be made available on the NETTAG+ website.

Note that the Seminar presentation offers theoretical knowledge intended as a foundation for all subsequent workshops. If partners opt to combine certain workshops in the same event, it's recommended to categorize them by theme and potentially divide the Seminar presentation accordingly. To facilitate this process, the slides corresponding to each workshop have been identified.

2.3 Workshop #2 - Marine litter produced on board

2.3.1 Overview

The second participatory workshop is entitled 'Marine litter produced on board' and aims to raise awareness about the marine litter produced on board by the fishing vessels, its proper management and to foster behavioural change towards the adoption of best practices. The specific objectives of the workshop are to:

- Educate and raise awareness among participants regarding the importance of tackling marine litter issues and implementing on-board best practices.
- Identify common items of marine litter generated on board (e.g., old gear, fish containers, oils).
- Engage participants in defining effective on-board practices for managing the marine litter produced.
- Gather suggestions on how to disseminate information and encourage other fishers to adopt similar practices.

This workshop involves informative and hands-on exercises and will take approximately two hours (see the proposed agenda in Annex 11).

2.3.2 *Workshop development*

Registration

The registration team welcome the participants and hand them the Participant Information Sheet (Annex 1), two Informed Consent Forms (Annex 2), and the Feedback Form (Annex 4). Participants are asked to sign the presence list (Annex 3) and return the signed informed consent form (each participant should keep a copy for themselves).

Welcome (plenary)

| 10 minutes

Participants are welcomed, followed by a quick presentation of the objectives and the activities planned for the workshop. The participants will randomly be divided into small groups, with a maximum of six elements.

Exercise 1: Litter classification (group)

| 20 minutes

Participants in each group start by nominating a spokesperson to present the results at the plenary sessions. Then, participants are asked to classify various litter items, represented by images on printed cards (Annex 12), as litter or non-litter by placing each item in the corresponding section on the exercise sheet (Figure 2; Annex 13). Once a consensus is reached, participants write the name of each item in the appropriate column, to be presented in the plenary session.

Exercise 1: Classify each item as litter or non-litter

NON-LITTER	LITTER

Exercise 1 | Group _____
Workshop #2 'Marine litter produced on board' | [add the location of the workshop] . [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Figure 2. Example of the first exercise sheet (workshop #2)

Exercise 2: Litter destination (group)

| 20 minutes

The second exercise is divided into two parts and aims to identify the destination of litter items (identified in the previous exercise), based on participants' fishing experience.

In the first part of the exercise (Exercise 2A), participants are asked to distinguish between litter items thrown overboard and litter brought to shore. Once a consensus is reached, participants write the name of each item in the appropriate column on the exercise sheet (Figure 3; Annex 13), to be presented in the plenary session.

In the second part of the exercise (Exercise 2B), participants are asked to identify the ultimate destination of litter items brought to shore. Litter items previously identified as 'Bring to shore' should be allocated to one of the following destinations: i) stays on port, ii) deposited in a general garbage container, or iii) sent for recycling. Once a consensus is reached, participants write the name of each item in the appropriate column of the exercise sheet (Figure 4; Annex 13), to be presented in the plenary session.

Exercise 2A: Based on your own experience, identify the destination of each litter item

THROW OVERBOARD	BRING TO SHORE

Exercise 2A | Group
Workshop #1 'Marine litter produced on board' | *[add the location of the workshop]* . [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Figure 3. Example of the sheet for exercise 2A (workshop #2)

Exercise 2B: Based on your own experience, identify the destination of each litter item that is brought to shore

STAYS ON PORT	GENERAL GARBAGE CONTAINER	RECYCLING

Exercise 2B | Group
Workshop #1 'Marine litter produced on board' | *[add the location of the workshop]* . [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Figure 4. Example of the sheet for exercise 2B (workshop #2)

Presentation of results & discussion (*plenary*)

| 20 minutes

Following the initial two exercises, participants convene in the plenary session to share and deliberate on the outcomes. Each group's spokesperson displays the exercise sheets and presents the group's findings. A discussion among participants regarding the chosen destination for litter is encouraged (e.g. which items were not properly classified as litter/non-litter; was the destination most accurate? why wasn't litter separated for recycling?). At the end, the moderators present the correct results, fostering a reassessment of the initial evaluations.

Exercise 3: Further actions and dissemination (*group*)

| 20 minutes

Back on groups, and based on previous discussions, participants are asked to give suggestions to reduce the marine litter produced on board and select measures to be implemented on board and at ports. Then, they are asked to identify internal and external factors that can influence the success of the proposed measures through a SWOT analysis. After reaching consensus, participants write their suggestions on the exercise sheet (Figure 5; Annex 13).

General guidelines to explain the SWOT analysis to fishers:

- **Strengths:** Things that fishers are really good at or have an advantage (e.g. extensive knowledge of local marine ecosystems and fishing practices, strong sense of community and cooperation, a positive attitude and willingness to adopt new practices, adaptability).
- **Weaknesses:** Areas that need improvement (e.g. lack of awareness about new methods, difficulties in accessing information or financial resources, resistance to change).
- **Opportunities:** External factors or chances for positive developments in fishing practices (e.g. policies (e.g. EU Directive 2019/883) and subsidies that encourage and financially assist the adoption of better practices, advancements in technology such as efficient gear designs or waste management tools, market demand for eco-friendly practices, opportunities to enhance the community's reputation).
- **Threats:** External factors that could pose challenges or risks to fishing practices (e.g. lack of enforcement, lack of infrastructures, economic factors, environmental changes).

- Five exercise sheets per group (in A3 format) numbered with the practical exercise to be completed (Annex 13),
- Colourful pens.

In case partners decide to provide a theoretical background on the marine litter theme, the seminar slides corresponding to workshop 2 can be used (Annex 10). All educational materials are available in the project share point and will be translated to local languages (Portuguese, Spanish, Italian and Croatian). After the awareness actions, these materials will be made available on the NETTAG+ website.

2.4 Workshop #3 - Marine litter collected by fishing gear

2.4.1 Overview

The third participatory workshop is entitled 'Marine litter collected by fishing gear' and aims to raise awareness about passively fished waste, its proper management and to foster behavioural change towards the adoption of best practices. The specific objectives of the workshop are to:

- Educate and raise awareness among participants regarding the importance of managing correctly the litter collected by fishing nets.
- Identify common items of marine litter passively fished, including domestic litter, industrial litter, fisheries debris.
- Engage participants in defining effective practices regarding waste management.
- Stimulate discussions among participants regarding the fisheries' role as 'Cleaners of the Ocean' and explore strategies to inspire them to actively contribute to the mission of collecting marine litter.

This workshop involves informative and hands-on exercises and will take approximately two hours (see the proposed agenda in Annex 14).

2.4.2 Workshop development

Registration

The registration team welcome the participants and hand them the Participant Information Sheet (Annex 1), two Informed Consent Forms (Annex 2), and the Feedback form (Annex 4). Participants are asked to sign the presence list (Annex 3) and return the signed informed consent form (each participant should keep a copy for themselves).

Welcome (plenary)

| 10 minutes

Participants are welcomed, followed by a quick presentation of the objectives and the activities planned for the workshop. The participants will randomly be divided into small groups, with a maximum of six elements.

Exercise 1: Litter passively caught in fishing nets (group)

| 20 minutes

Participants in each group start by nominating a spokesperson to present the results at the plenary sessions. Then, participants are asked to register the litter items commonly caught by their fishing nets on the exercise sheet (Figure 7; Annex 15).

Exercise 1: Based on your own experience, register the litter items commonly caught in your fishing nets

DOMESTIC LITTER	FISHERIES DEBRIS	OTHER

NETTAG+ Exercise 1 | Group
Workshop #3 'Marine litter collected by fishing gears' | [add the location of the workshop] , [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Figure 7. Example of the first exercise sheet (workshop #3)

Exercise 2: Destination of litter caught in fishing nets (group)

| 20 minutes

The second exercise is divided in two parts and aims to identify the destination of litter items caught in the fishing nets, based on participants' fishing experience.

In the first part of the exercise (Exercise 2A), participants are asked to distinguish between litter items thrown overboard and litter brought to shore. Once a consensus is reached, participants write the name of each item in the appropriate column on the exercise sheet (Figure 8; Annex 15), to be presented in the plenary session.

Exercise 2B: Based on your own experience, register the destination of each litter item (capture in fishing nets) that is brought to shore

STAYS ON PORT	GENERAL GARBAGE CONTAINER	RECYCLING

Exercise 2B | Group _____
Workshop #3 'Marine litter collected by fishing gears' | *[add the location of the workshop]*, [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Figure 9. Example of the sheet for exercise 2B (workshop #3)

Exercise 3: Further actions and dissemination (group)

| 20 minutes

Back on groups, and based on previous discussions, participants are asked to suggest measures (on board and at ports) to encourage the collection and proper management of marine litter, during normal fishing activities, and to identify internal and external factors that can influence the success of the proposed measures through a SWOT analysis. After reaching consensus, participants write their suggestions on the exercise sheet (Figure 10; Annex 15).

Finally, participants are asked to propose methods for disseminating best practices to fellow fishers, ways of motivating them to embrace the role of ‘Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean’ and to identify either individual fishers, vessels or communities that demonstrate leadership and social influence in terms of supporting innovation and sustainable behaviours relating to litter. Participants’ willingness to create or contribute to a marine litter platform should also be explored, as well as the type of data they would be willing to report (e.g., weight, typology, location/coordinates) and in what circumstances (e.g., rewards, training, collaboration with other entity responsible for litter analysis and registration). Once consensus is reached, participants write their suggestions on the exercise sheet (Figure 11; Annex 15).

Presentation of results & discussion (plenary)

| 20 minutes

Following the exercise, participants convene in the plenary session to share and deliberate on the outcomes. Each group's spokesperson displays the exercise sheets and presents the collective suggestions. This moment can be used to discuss the Clean Ocean Day event (demonstration event of WP2, Task 2.4), its logistics, and to ask participants about their availability to get involved. At the end, moderators provide a summary of the suggestions put forth by all groups.

Workshop final conclusions (plenary)

| 10 minutes

The workshop concludes with the presentation of final conclusions, encouraging participants to share additional insights or address any lingering questions. Participants are invited to complete the feedback form and to leave it at the registration table.

2.4.3 Resources and materials

A set of materials will be available to participants at the group tables to fulfil the workshop exercises, namely:

- Five exercise sheets per group (in A3 format) numbered with the practical exercise to be completed (Annex 15),
- Colourful pens.

In case partners decide to provide a theoretical background on the marine litter theme, the seminar slides corresponding to workshop 3 can be used (Annex 10). All educational materials are available in the project share point and will be translated to local languages (Portuguese, Spanish, Italian and Croatian). After the awareness actions, these materials will be made available on the NETTAG+ website.

2.5 Workshop #4 - Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation

2.5.1 Overview

The fourth participatory workshop is entitled 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' and aims to raise awareness about the incidental capture of non-target species, particularly sensitive endangered species (such as sea turtles, marine mammals, seabirds, sharks, sponges and corals). The specific objectives of the workshop are to:

- Raise awareness among fishers about the importance of reducing bycatch in fishing.
- Familiarise participants with various devices and techniques used to minimise bycatch.
- Provide guidelines and best practices for acting in case of bycatch.
- Promote the adoption of sustainable practices that benefit the health of marine ecosystems.

This workshop involves informative and hands-on exercises and will take approximately two hours (see the proposed agenda in Annex 16).

2.5.2 *Workshop development*

Registration

The registration team welcome the participants and hand them the Participant Information Sheet (Annex 1), two Informed Consent Forms (Annex 2), and the Feedback form (Annex 4). Participants are asked to sign the presence list (Annex 3) and return the signed informed consent form (each participant should keep a copy for themselves).

Welcome (*plenary*)

| 10 minutes

Participants are welcomed, followed by a quick presentation of the objectives and the activities planned for the workshop. Finally, the participants will randomly be divided into small groups, with a maximum of six elements.

Exercise 1: Species commonly captured (*group*)

| 20 minutes

Participants in each group start by nominating a spokesperson to present the results at the plenary sessions. A facilitated open discussion is encouraged so participants share their bycatch experiences. Then, participants are asked to:

- Identify non-target species commonly captured,
- Rank these species based on capture frequency,
- Associate captured species with the specific fishing gear used,
- Identify endangered species among the captured ones.

Printed cards with images of common bycatch species (e.g. seabirds, marine mammals, turtles, sharks, sponges and corals; Annex 17) are provided to support the exercise. Once a consensus is reached, participants write their answers on the exercise sheet (Figure 12; Annex 18).

Exercise 1: Based on your experience, register the species commonly involved in bycatch, link them to the fishing gears, identify the endangered species

BYCATCH SPECIES PER FISHING GEAR

	BYCATCH SPECIES:	FISHING GEAR:
more captured		
✓		
✓		
✓		
✓		
✓		
✓		
✓		
✓		
✓		
less captured		

ENDANGERED SPECIES

Exercise 1 | Group _____
 Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | [add the location of the workshop] .
 [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Figure 12. Example of the first exercise sheet (workshop #4)

Exercise 2: Best practices to reduce bycatch (group)

| 20 minutes

In the second exercise, participants are asked to deliberate on the practicality and applicability of best practices. To facilitate the conversation, a table summarising available best practices for reducing bycatch will be provided (Annex 19). Participants are asked to i) identify the most suitable practices for their needs (given the fishing gear used and common bycatch species), ii) discuss ways of implementing them on board, and iii) discuss major strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. Key conclusions drawn from this discussion should be registered in the exercise sheet (Figure 13; Annex 18).

Exercise 3: Protocols in case of bycatch (group)

| 20 minutes

In the third exercise, participants are asked to deliberate on i) the rapid response protocols and on-board handling practices in case of bycatch, ii) the importance of communicating and notifying the relevant authorities, as well as iii) major strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. The discussion should extend to methods of implementing these protocols/practices. Key conclusions drawn from this discussion should be registered in the exercise sheet (Figure 14; Annex 18).

Exercise 2: Based on your experience, which measures can you adopt to reduce bycatch?

MINIMISATION MEASURES	SWOT ANALYSIS
<p>MEASURES TO REDUCE BYCATCH</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ <p>HOW TO IMPLEMENT THE SELECTED MEASURES?</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	<p>STRENGTHS (what you're good at)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>THREATS (risks or challenges)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>

Exercise 2 | Group
 Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | [add the location of the workshop] .
 [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Figure 13. Example of the second exercise sheet (workshop #4)

Exercise 3: Based on your experience, how do you handle bycatch and which protocols /best practices can you adopt in case of bycatch?

BEST PRACTICES/ PROTOCOLS	SWOT ANALYSIS
<p>COMMON PRACTICES IN CASE OF BYCATCH:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>NOTIFICATION (competent authorities, other):</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>ARE THERE IMPLEMENTED PROTOCOLS?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO IF YES, WHICH?</p> <p>SUGGESTIONS:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	<p>STRENGTHS (what you're good at)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>THREATS (risks or challenges)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>

Exercise 3 | Group
 Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | [add the location of the workshop] .
 [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Figure 14. Example of the third exercise sheet (workshop #4)

2.5.3 Resources and materials

A set of materials will be available to participants at the group tables to fulfil the workshop exercises, namely:

- Printed cards with images of the most common bycatch species (Annex 17),
- One A4 table per group summarising existing solutions to reduce bycatch (Annex 19),
- Four exercise sheets per group (in A3 format) numbered with the practical exercise to be completed (Annex 18),
- Colourful pens.

In case partners decide to provide a theoretical background on the bycatch theme, the seminar slides corresponding to workshop 4 can be used (Annex 10). All educational materials are available in the project share point and will be translated to local languages (Portuguese, Spanish, Italian and Croatian). After the awareness actions, these materials will be made available on the NETTAG+ website.

2.6 Workshop #5 - Reducing fisheries footprint

2.6.1 Overview

The fifth participatory workshop is entitled 'Reducing fisheries footprint' and aims to raise awareness and assess the viability of reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and avoiding/reducing the use of plastics to foster a reduction of fisheries ecological footprint. The specific objectives of the workshop are to:

- Educate and raise awareness about the importance of joining the global efforts on the energy transition by improving the fisheries energy efficiency and reducing greenhouse gas emissions.
- Educate and raise awareness about the importance of reducing the use of plastic by replacing it by alternative/eco-friendly materials, whenever possible and adequate.
- Familiarise participants with best practices and promote its adoption.

This workshop involves informative and hands-on exercises and will take approximately one hour and forty minutes (see the proposed agenda in Annex 20).

2.6.2 Workshop development

Registration

The registration team welcome the participants and hand them the Participant Information Sheet (Annex 1), two Informed Consent Forms (Annex 2), and the Feedback form (Annex 4). Participants are asked to sign the presence list and return the signed informed consent form (each participant should keep a copy for themselves).

Welcome (*plenary*)

| 10 minutes

Participants are welcomed, followed by a quick presentation of the objectives and the activities planned for the workshop. Finally, the participants will randomly be divided into small groups, with a maximum of six elements.

Exercise 1: Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions (*group*)

| 20 minutes

Participants in each group start by nominating a spokesperson to present the results at the plenary sessions. Then, participants are asked to discuss the feasibility of GHG emissions reduction measures, identify the most suitable for their reality and discuss ways of implementing them on board (including a SWOT analysis). To support the exercise, a list of potential measures to reduce GHG emissions will be provided to support the discussion (Annex 21). Key conclusions should be registered in the exercise sheet (Figure 16; Annex 22).

Exercise 2: Use of alternative/eco-friendly materials (*group*)

| 20 minutes

Participants are asked to discuss ways of reducing the use of plastics, using alternative or eco-friendly materials and to discuss ways of implementing these measures (including a SWOT analysis). A list of activities and materials commonly used during fishing operations was prepared to initiate and support the discussion (Annex 23). Key conclusions should be registered in the exercise sheet (Figure 17; Annex 22).

Exercise 1: Based on your experience, which measures can you adopt to reduce greenhouse gas emissions? How to implement them?

ENERGY TRANSITION	SWOT ANALYSIS
<p>MEASURES TO REDUCE GHG EMISSIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ <p>HOW TO IMPLEMENT THE SELECTED MEASURES?</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	<p>STRENGTHS (what you're good at)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>THREATS (risks or challenges)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>

Exercise 1 | Group
 Workshop #5 'Sustainable practices: reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and use of alternative/eco-friendly materials' | *[add the location of the workshop]* , *[dd/mm/yyyy]*

Figure 16. Example of the first exercise sheet (workshop #5)

Exercise 2: Based on your experience, which materials can be replaced to reduce fishers' reliance on plastics? How to implement them?

ECO-FRIENDLY MATERIALS	SWOT ANALYSIS
<p>WHICH MATERIALS CAN BE REPLACED?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ <p>HOW TO IMPLEMENT THIS MEASURES?</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	<p>STRENGTHS (what you're good at)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>THREATS (risks or challenges)</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>

Exercise 2 | Group
 Workshop #5 'Sustainable practices: reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and use of alternative/eco-friendly materials' | *[add the location of the workshop]* , *[dd/mm/yyyy]*

Figure 17. Example of the second exercise sheet (workshop #5)

2.6.3 Resources and materials

A set of materials will be available to participants at the group tables to fulfil the workshop exercises, namely:

- One A4 sheet per group with examples of best practices to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Annex 21),
- One A4 sheet per group with examples of activities and materials that have the potential to be replaced with eco-friendly materials (Annex 23),
- Three exercise sheets per group (in A3 format) numbered with the practical exercise to be completed (Annex 22),
- Colourful pens.

In case partners decide to provide a theoretical background on the energy transition and use of alternative/eco-friendly materials theme, the seminar slides corresponding to workshop 5 can be used (Annex 10). All educational materials are available in the project share point and will be translated to local languages. After the awareness actions, these materials will be made available on the NETTAG+ website.

2.7 Workshop #6 - NETTAG+ solutions

2.7.1 Overview

The sixth participatory workshop is entitled 'NETTAG+ solutions' and aims to assess fishers' overall perception of the three solutions proposed by the NETTAG+ project, namely:

- PREVENT marine litter derived from fisheries activities.
- AVOID loss of fishing gear using acoustic tags and autonomous vehicles.
- MITIGATE harmful impacts by developing technology to help map and retrieving existing ALDFG.

The specific objectives of the workshop are to:

- Present the NETTAG+ technological solutions and awareness actions designed to prevent, avoid, and mitigate the harmful impacts of fishing gear.
- Evaluate the applicability and effectiveness of both technological and awareness approaches as reliable solutions for future implementation.

This workshop involves informative and hands-on exercises and will take approximately one hour and a half (see the proposed agenda in Annex 24).

2.7.2 Workshop development

Registration

The registration team welcome the participants and hand them the Participant Information Sheet (Annex 1), two Informed Consent Forms (Annex 2), and the Feedback form (Annex 4). Participants are asked to sign the presence list and return the signed informed consent form (each participant should keep a copy for themselves).

Welcome & Talk on the NETTAG+ solutions (*plenary*)

| 30 minutes

Participants are welcomed, followed by a quick presentation of the objectives and the activities planned for the workshop. The three NETTAG+ solutions to prevent, avoid and mitigate the harmful impacts of fishing gear are presented. Following the presentation, participants are encouraged to pose questions and engage in a discussion on the NETTAG+ solutions.

Exercise 1: General evaluation of the NETTAG+ solutions (*plenary*)

| 10 minutes

The participants are asked to provide a general evaluation of each NETTAG+ solution by placing coloured dot stickers (green, yellow, or red) in the posters displayed on the wall (Figure 19; Annex 25). Then, the participants will randomly be divided into small groups, with a maximum of six elements.

Exercise 2: Discussion of the NETTAG+ solutions (*group*)

| 20 minutes

The participants are asked to discuss the applicability and effectiveness of the different NETTAG+ solutions as reliable solutions for future implementation and encouraging behavioural changes (e.g. is the solution easy to implement, is it affordable, is it user-friendly, will be well received by fishers, will it produce the expected results). Participants are also tasked to propose suggestions to overcome the identified challenges, as well as suggestions and upgrades to the NETTAG+ solutions. Key conclusions should be registered in the exercise sheets (Figure 20, Figure 21, Figure 22; Annex 26).

	PREVENT	AVOID	MITIGATE
AWARENESS ACTIONS			
PORT FACILITIES & PLANS			
FISHERS REWARD PROGRAM			

NETTAG+ Exercise 1 Evaluate each NETTAG+ solution by placing a colored sticker (green, yellow or red) in each box
 Workshop #6 'NETTAG+ solutions' | [add the location of the workshop] , [dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 19. Example of the poster for the evaluation of the NETTAG+ solutions (workshop #6)

PREVENT	ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES	SUGGESTIONS / UPGRADES
AWARENESS ACTIONS	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓
PORT FACILITIES & PLANS	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓
FISHERS REWARD PROGRAM	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

NETTAG+ Exercise 2A | Group _____
 Workshop #6 'NETTAG+ solutions' | [add the location of the workshop] , [dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 20. Example of the second exercise sheet for PREVENT solutions (workshop #6)

AVOID

	ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES	SUGGESTIONS / UPGRADES
ACOUSTIC TAGS	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓

NETTAG+ Exercise 2B | Group _____
Workshop #6 'NETTAG+ solutions' | [add the location of the workshop] , [dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 21. Example of the second exercise sheet for AVOID solutions (workshop #6)

MITIGATE

	ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES	SUGGESTIONS / UPGRADES
DETECTION OF LOST GEARS	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
MAPPING ROBOT	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓
	✓	✓	✓

NETTAG+ Exercise 2C | Group _____
Workshop #6 'NETTAG+ solutions' | [add the location of the workshop] , [dd/mm/yyyy]

Figure 22. Example of the second exercise sheet for MITIGATE solutions (workshop #6)

Presentation of results & discussion (plenary)

| 20 minutes

Following the group exercise, participants convene in the plenary session to share and deliberate on the outcomes. Each group's spokesperson displays the exercise sheets and present the group's findings. A discussion among participants is encouraged and, at the end, moderators provide a summary of the suggestions put forth by all groups.

Workshop final conclusions (plenary)

| 10 minutes

The workshop concludes with the presentation of final conclusions, encouraging participants to share additional insights or address any lingering questions. Participants are invited to complete the feedback form and to leave it at the registration table.

2.7.3 Resources and materials

A set of materials will be available to participants to fulfil the workshop exercises, namely:

- One wall poster (in A3 format) to be used in the first exercise (Annex 25),
- Three exercise sheets per group (in A3 format) numbered with the practical exercise to be completed (Annex 26),
- Colourful dot stickers (green, yellow, red),
- Post-its and pens.

To introduce the NETTAG+ solutions, the project general presentation (Annex 8) can be used and updated to incorporate developments from the work packages. All educational materials are available in the project share point and will be translated to local languages.

3 Concluding remarks

Awareness actions are a crucial step in the comprehensive approach undertaken by NETTAG+ to address marine litter and ALDFG issues within professional fishing communities across the Atlantic and Mediterranean regions. The educational materials, designed and tailored to the specific needs and contexts of the target audience, will serve as foundational resources during the series of participatory workshops organized by NETTAG+ fishers' representatives in Portugal, Spain, Malta, Italy, and Croatia.

By engaging participants in interactive learning experiences (participatory workshops) and facilitating discussions around marine litter prevention and co-design of best practices for environmental-friendly fishing methods, the educational materials were designed to empower fishing communities with the necessary background knowledge and skills to increase responsible use behaviour. Moreover, the educational materials were produced following the approach 'from fishers to fishers' to guarantee that NETTAG+ outputs align with the needs of the fishing community and to foster ownership and increase the likelihood of influencing behavioural changes.

To ensure widespread accessibility and dissemination, all educational resources and materials generated will be made readily available on the NETTAG+ project website, serving as tools to raise awareness and for advocacy beyond the immediate scope of the project.

References

- Iñiguez M.E., Conesa J.A., Fullana A., 2016. Marine debris occurrence and treatment: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 64: 394-402. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2016.06.03
- Brown J. & Macfadyen G., 2007. Ghost fishing in European waters: Impacts and management responses. *Marine Policy*, 31: 488-504. doi:10.1016/j.marpol.2006.10.007
- Drinkwin J., 2020. *Effective ghost gear solutions: learning from what works*. Global Ghost Gear Initiative 2020
- Freire J. & García-Allut A., 1999. *Integration of fishers' ecological knowledge in fisheries biology and management. A proposal for the case of the artisanal coastal fisheries of Galicia (NW Spain)*. Paper presented at the ICES CM 1999
- Pita. P., Antelo M., Hyder K., Vingada J., Villasante S., 2020. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 7 doi:10.3389/fmars.2020.00242

Annex 1. Participant information sheet

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

Participant information sheet

Note: items marked in yellow need to be completed by the NETTAG+ partner using the participant information sheet in their NETTAG+ activities.

NETTAG+ is a three-year research project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program (Grant No. 101112812), aiming to PREVENT, AVOID and MITIGATE the environmentally harmful impacts of fishing gear and their associated marine litter, actively contributing to the European Commission Mission “Restore our ocean and waters by 2030”.

Purpose of the study

Marine litter is a global problem and requires cooperation across the science-policy-society interface, combining the know-how of the different actors involved to successfully navigate towards innovative solutions. Based on synergistic activities between the fisheries industry, scientists and NGOs, NETTAG+ aims to develop three solutions to PREVENT, AVOID and MITIGATE the harmful impacts of lost fishing gear on marine life and habitats.

To PREVENT marine litter derived from fisheries activities, NETTAG+ prepared a package of six workshops targeting professional fishers from the North-East Atlantic (Portugal, Spain) and the Mediterranean (Italy, Croatia, Malta):

- Workshop #1 - Seminar on marine litter
- Workshop #2 - Marine litter produced on board
- Workshop #3 - Marine litter collected by fishing gears
- Workshop #4 - Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation
- Workshop #5 - Reducing fisheries footprint
- Workshop #6 - NETTAG+ solutions

The participatory workshops will be delivered by the fishers’ association and representatives, beneficiaries of the project. With the development of these workshops, NETTAG+ aims to enhance the comprehension of marine litter issues within professional fishing communities and to foster a transformation in the fisheries industry's perception, shifting from being perceived as a 'polluter' to becoming a 'guardian and cleaner' of the ocean.

Photography and/or video recording will be taking place during the workshops to be used within the scope of the NETTAG+ project activities, including reporting and dissemination.

1/3

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide to participate in the NETTAG+ workshops and it is completely voluntary. We have provided information on this document about the NETTAG+ project to support your decision and the technical team will be happy to answer any questions that you may have. You will then be asked to sign a consent form agreeing to take part. Nevertheless, you are free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without prejudice or negative consequences.

What are the benefits of participating?

The NETTAG+ workshops will empower professional fishers (from small-scale and industrial fisheries) to build upon its role as key players in tackling marine litter and adopting environmentally friendly fishing techniques, changing the current perception of the fisheries industry as 'polluter' to 'guardian and cleaner' of the ocean.

Moreover, your knowledge and expertise will help co-creating innovative solutions to promote or implement best practices for waste management on fishing vessels and at fishing ports.

Will my participation in the study be kept confidential?

All the information we receive from you, including your name and any other identifying information (if applicable), will be strictly confidential and only accessible by NETTAG+ partners. Any information about you which is published will have your name and contact details removed so that you cannot be recognised unless you have given such permission.

As photography and/or video recording will be taking place during the workshop, your footage or images, taken in the natural course of proceedings, will be published in the context of the event.

Project coordinator

CIIMAR - Centro Interdisciplinar de Investigação Marinha e Ambiental

Terminal de Cruzeiros do Porto de Leixões

Av. General Norton de Matos, s/n

4450-208 Matosinhos, Portugal

<https://www2.ciimar.up.pt/>

2/3

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

Partners

The NETTAG+ consortium is composed by an international and multidisciplinary team, comprising 15 participants from 7 different countries, bringing together complementary expertise in various areas of knowledge and a robust academia-industry collaboration:

[CIIMAR](#) - Centro Interdisciplinar de Investigação Marinha e Ambiental (Portugal)

[INEC TEC](#) - Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência (Portugal)

[USC](#) - Universidad de Santiago de Compostela (Spain)

[UNEW](#) – Newcastle University (United Kingdom)

[UA](#) - Universidade de Aveiro (Portugal)

[WWF](#) - World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF Med, WWF Italy, WWF Adria)

[ERINN](#) - ERINN Innovation (Ireland)

[ARVI](#) - Cooperativa de Armadores de Pesca del Puerto de Vigo (Spain)

[APMSHM](#) - Associação Pró-Maior Segurança dos Homens do Mar (Portugal)

[MAFA](#) - Ministry for Agriculture, Fisheries, and Animal Rights

[CoGePa](#) - Co.Ge.Pa. di Portorosa (Italy)

[SF](#) - Succorfish (United Kingdom)

[C&S](#) - Cadilhe & Santos (Portugal)

Further information and contact details

1. For general information about the NETTAG+ project please visit <https://nettagplus.eu/>.

2. For specific information about the NETTAG+ project on **[partner organisation's name]**: contact **[Responsible person name and email]**

3/3

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Annex 2. Informed consent form

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

NETTAG+ Informed Consent Form

Note: Items marked in yellow need to be completed by the NETTAG+ partner using the informed consent form in their NETTAG+ activities. This template should be revised by partners in accordance with national legislation.

We are asking if you would like to take part in the NETTAG+ project. Before you consent your participation in this study, please read the participant information sheet, and in case of any question or queries, please ask to the NETTAG+ team. If you do not agree to the collection of personal data by the NETTAG+ project, unfortunately, you cannot participate in the NETTAG+ study.

The NETTAG+ consortium asks for your consent for the following:

- ✓ I am voluntarily taking part in this study (unpaid) and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason, without any consequences. To exercise these rights, please send a written request to the Sandra Ramos email: sramos@ciimar.up.pt.
- ✓ I have read the Participation Information Sheet and fully understand what is expected of me within this study.
- ✓ I have had the opportunity to ask questions and queries, which were answered by the NETTAG+ team.
- ✓ I understand that my answers and contributions will be recorded on paper and later entered into a computer database.
- ✓ I understand that any information I give will be anonymised and may be published.
- ✓ I understand that once my data have been anonymised and incorporated into themes it might not be possible for it to be withdrawn, although every attempt will be made to extract my data, up to the point of publication.
- ✓ I consent that information from my participation will be used in reports, conferences and events.
- ✓ I consent that [NETTAG+ partner organisation's name] will keep copies of any information I give for 10 years after the study has finished.

1/2

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

- ✓ I consent to my photographed being taken in the context of the NETTAG+ project and images where I appear to be used within the scope of the NETTAG+ project activities.
- ✓ I consent to my being filmed in the context of the NETTAG+ project and images where I appear to be used within the scope of the NETTAG+ project activities.

Participant Full Name: _____

Participant email: _____

Date: __/__/__, in _____ *(Please indicate the place where the form is signed)*

(Signature according with identification document)

Annex 4. Template of the workshop feedback form

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

Feedback Form

We ask you to take a moment to provide your feedback on the workshop. Your responses will be used to improve future NETTAG+ workshops.

Name (optional): _____

On a scale of 1 to 4 where 1 is strongly disagree and 4 is strongly agree, please circle the most appropriate answer:

1. The Workshop venue was:

a) Comfortable	1	2	3	4
b) Well located	1	2	3	4
c) Food and refreshments were adequate	1	2	3	4

2. The Workshop content was:

a) Relevant	1	2	3	4
b) Comprehensive	1	2	3	4
c) Easy to understand	1	2	3	4

3. The Workshop was:

a) Well paced	1	2	3	4
b) Breaks were sufficient	1	2	3	4
c) A good mix between listening and activities	1	2	3	4

4. The facilitators were:

a) Knowledgeable	1	2	3	4
b) Well-prepared	1	2	3	4
c) Responsive to participant's questions	1	2	3	4

5. What did you like best about this Workshop?

6. What did you like least about this Workshop?

Thank you for participating, we appreciate your feedback.

 Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Annex 5. Structure of the synthesis report

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

Synthesis report of the participatory Workshop #_ [fill with the workshop number and name]

Date | Place

Introduction

Every year, tons of fishing gear are discarded to the ocean globally, inflicting severe threats to marine habitats and wildlife while causing economic damage to the fishing sector. Addressing marine pollution on a global scale requires cooperation across the science-policy-society interface, combining the know-how of the different actors involved.

NETTAG+ collaborates with the fisheries industry, scientists, and NGOs to develop solutions that PREVENT, AVOID, and MITIGATE the harmful impacts of lost fishing gears on marine life and habitats.

To PREVENT marine litter derived from fisheries activities, NETTAG+ prepared a package of six workshops targeting professional fishers from the North-East Atlantic (Portugal, Spain) and the Mediterranean (Italy, Croatia, Malta):

- Workshop #1 - Seminar on marine litter
- Workshop #2 - Marine litter produced on board
- Workshop #3 - Marine litter collected by fishing gears
- Workshop #4 - Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation
- Workshop #5 - Reducing fisheries footprint
- Workshop #6 - NETTAG+ solutions

With the development of participatory workshops, NETTAG+ aims to enhance the comprehension of marine litter issues within professional fishing communities and to foster a transformation in the fisheries industry's perception, shifting from being perceived as a 'polluter' to becoming a 'guardian and cleaner' of the ocean.

This report summarises the results from the NETTAG+ participatory workshop performed in ... [provide the name of the workshop and the region where the actions took place].

1

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

Workshop objectives and structure

[Indicate the purpose of the workshop, its objectives and general structure]

...

Workshops results

[Indicate the target audience (brief description of the participants preserving their anonymity, e.g., number of participants, type of fishing activity, no. of groups, no of participants per group, etc.). Then, describe the results obtained in each exercise e major conclusions form the discussion. Include photos from the event (group tables, plenary session, materials/exercise sheets).]

...

Workshop evaluation results

[Summarize the main results from the participants evaluation of the workshop]

...

Final considerations

...

Acknowledgements

[If applicable]

...

Annex 6. NETTAG+ flyer

Every year, tons of fishing gear are discarded to the ocean globally, inflicting **severe threats** to marine habitats and wildlife while causing **economic damage** to the **fishing sector**. The timely **tracking and recovery** of lost fishing gear can **minimize this risk**, help preserve our oceans and boost the fishing sector.

The three **NETTAG+** solutions will be tested, validated and demonstrated in real conditions in Atlantic and Mediterranean countries: Portugal, Spain, Italy, Croatia, Malta and United Kingdom

Through collaboration between the fisheries industry, scientists and NGOs, the NETTAG+ project aims to:

PREVENT
FISHERS AS GUARDIANS AND CLEANERS OF THE OCEAN

Empower the fisheries sector, namely professional fishers, to adopt more environmental-friendly fishing methods, prevent marine litter and increase responsible user behavior.

Create adequate conditions for the reception and treatment of litter at fishing ports, including through recycling and reuse.

Recognize and reward the volunteer service provided by fishers when retrieving marine litter that is passively collected in fishing gear.

AVOID
FISHING GEAR LOCATION WITH ACOUSTIC TAGS

Develop and engineer acoustic tags to be attached to fishing gear as a sustainable, low-cost and innovative low-impact solution to improve mapping, tracking and recovery of lost fishing gear.

Improve a robotic surface system linked with the acoustic tag system for lost fishing gear location/recovery.

MITIGATE
DETECTION AND REMOVAL OF ABANDONED, LOST OR OTHERWISE DISCARDED FISHING GEAR (ALDFG)

Develop a system to detect ALDFG in the Ocean water column and seabed.

Co-develop, with fishers, a robotic tool to detect, map, track and recover ALDFG.

NETTAG+ main actions:

- 1. **AWARENESS ACTIONS, PARTICIPATORY WORKSHOPS AND DEMONSTRATION EVENTS** with fishers on marine litter prevention and retrieval
- 2. **ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF ALDFG** and developed technological solutions
- 3. **DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF SMART AND ENVIRONMENTAL-FRIENDLY SOLUTIONS FOR ALDFG** prevention and retrieval, through tagging, mapping and recovering technological systems
- 4. **DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIONS** on NETTAG+ findings to policy-makers, industry, fishers, scientists, EU projects and the general public

What we aim to achieve:

- Successfully test and employ NETTAG+ tags to fishing gear to avoid lost and abandoned fishing gear (ALDFG)
- Work with fishers to be guardians and cleaners of our sea and tackling marine pollution.
- Contribute to Ocean health through retrieving operations and increased awareness.
- Reduce the negative impacts of ALDFG on marine life and habitats.

NETTAG+ brings together an international and multidisciplinary team from **7 different countries**, including scientists, the fishing industry, governmental fisheries authorities, NGOs, and technological and knowledge-management companies.

NETTAG+ targets groups:

- Fishers
- Fishing gear manufacturers
- Port authorities
- Policy makers
- Citizens

EU MISSIONS
RESTORE OUR CLEAN & WATER

The **NETTAG+** is a three-year project funded by the EU Horizon Europe program, actively contributing to the EU Mission: **Restore our ocean and waters by 2030**.

Follow us:
nettagplus.eu
 @NetTagProject

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAG+). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UK partners University of Newcastle Upon Tyne and Succorfish Ltd. are funded by the UKRI under the agreement on the association of the UK to Horizon Europe (Grant No. 10544822).

Annex 7. NETTAG+ roll-up banner

NETTAG+

Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

PREVENT
marine litter derived from fisheries activities
Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

AVOID
loss of fishing gears
Fishing Gears Location with Acoustic Tags

MITIGATE
harmful impacts of ALDFG
Detection and Removal of ALDFG

WORKING DIRECTLY WITH THE FISHING INDUSTRY

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant Agreement No. 101112812 (NETTAG+). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UK Research and Innovation

UK Partners on NETTAG+ are supported by UKRI under the UK Government's Horizon Europe Funding guarantee. Grant No. 10066822 (University of Newcastle upon Tyne), (Succorfish Ltd.)

Annex 8. Proposed agenda for Workshop #1

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

1st WORKSHOP Seminar on marine litter

Agenda

Place | Date | Time

- | | |
|----------------------|---|
| 13:45 - 14:00 | Registration |
| 14:00 - 14:15 | Welcome and presentation of the NETTAG+ project |
| 14:15 - 15:15 | Seminar on Marine Litter |
| 15:15 - 15:30 | Discussion |
| 15:30 - 15:50 | Coffee Break |

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Annex 9. NETTAG+ general presentation

Presentation of the NETTAG+ project

Partner | Date

www.nettagplus.eu Follow @NetTagProject

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program. Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

NETTAG+ project

NETTAG+ Preventing, avoiding and mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gear and associated marine litter

- ✓ Funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program
- ✓ Three-year project: 01/05/2023 to 30/04/2026
- ✓ Coordination: CIMAR – Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research (Portugal)
- ✓ Contributes to the European Commission Mission 'Restore our ocean and waters by 2030'
- ✓ NETTAG+ aims to **upgrade** and **upscale** the integrative preventive approach that started in the previous NetTag project (2019-2021), and to replicate it in Mediterranean regions

Funded by the European Union

NETTAG+ consortium

Multidisciplinary and international team

15 partners from **7 different countries** with a strong academia-industry collaboration

Funded by the European Union

NETTAG+ overview

Based on synergistic activities between the fisheries industry, scientists and NGOs, NETTAG+ is developing three solutions to PREVENT, AVOID and MITIGATE the harmful impacts of fishing gear

PREVENT

Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

AVOID

Fishing Gear Location with Acoustic Tags

MITIGATE

Detection and Removal of Abandoned, Lost or otherwise Discarded Fishing Gear (ALDFG)

NETTAG+ objectives

PREVENT

Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

- ✓ **Empower the fisheries sector**, namely professional fishers, **to adopt more environmental-friendly** fishing methods, **prevent marine litter** and increase responsible user behaviour.
- ✓ **Create adequate conditions** for the reception and treatment of litter **at fishing ports**, including through recycling and reuse.
- ✓ **Recognize and reward the volunteer service** provided by fishers when retrieving marine litter that is passively collected in fishing gear.

NETTAG+ objectives

AVOID

Fishing Gear Location with Acoustic Tags

- ✓ Develop and engineer **acoustic tags** to be attached to fishing gear as a sustainable, low-cost and innovative low-impact solution to improve mapping, tracking and recovery of lost fishing gear.
- ✓ Improve a **robotic surface system** linked with the acoustic tag system for lost fishing gear location/recovery.

NETTAG+ objectives

MITIGATE

Detection and Removal of Abandoned, Lost or otherwise Discarded Fishing Gear (ALDFG)

- ✓ Develop a **system to detect ALDFG** in the Ocean water column and seabed.
- ✓ Co-develop, with fishers, a **robotic tool to detect, map, track and recover ALDFG**.

NETTAG+ demonstrative events

The three NETTAG+ solutions will be **tested, validated and demonstrated in real conditions** in **Atlantic and Mediterranean countries: Portugal, Spain, Italy, Croatia, Malta and United Kingdom**

WP3 PREVENT

Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

WP2 AVOID

Fishing Gear Location with Acoustic Tags

WP4 MITIGATE

Detection and Removal of ALDFG (Map, Track and Recover)

Thank you

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

www.nettagplus.eu

Follow @NetTagProject

Annex 10. Seminar on marine litter presentation

NETTAG+

Seminar on Marine Litter

Participatory Workshop #1

Funded by the European Union
Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Indicate the place | Indicate the date dd/mm/yyyy

NETTAG+

TRANSPORT
the ocean is essential for marine transportation

CLIMATE REGULATION
covering 70% of the Earth's surface, helps to regulate the climate

AIR WE BREATHE
produces over half of the world's oxygen

BLUE ECONOMY
several billions euros are generated from the oceans

RECREATION
provides unique activities, such as fishing, surfing, diving.

FOOD
source of seafood, fish and essential ingredients

MEDICINE
many medical products come from the ocean

IMPORTANCE OF OUR OCEAN

Based on: <https://oceanservice.noaa.gov/facts/why-care-about-ocean.html>

W2&W3

Main ocean threats

NETTAG+

PLASTIC/MARINE POLLUTION

OVER-FISHING

OCEAN WARMING

ACIDIFICATION

EUTROPHICATION

14 LIFE BELOW WATER

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

UN, 2022: <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2022/img/info/Goal-14.pdf>

W2&W3

Where does it come from?

20%
comes from the sea

- Lost shipping containers
- Lost/discharged maritime activities gear (e.g. fisheries, aquaculture, shipping, oil platforms, wind farms)

Ocean is the final destination of litter!

80%
comes from the land

Major causes are poor waste management and littering on land

- Litter dropped in cities, at the beach,
- Industrial waste discharges
- Litter blown by the wind
- Poorly managed landfills
- Microbeads from hygiene products
- Sewage related litter

Funded by the European Union

Based on EEA, 2023 From source to sea – The untold story of marine litter

W&W3

Where does it go?

A significant amount of the marine litter is located at the sea bottom!

70% of marine litter is in the sea bottom

15% water surface and column

15% beaches and coastal waters

Funded by the European Union

Percentages from UNEP (2009) - Marine Litter: An Analytical Overview

W&W3

Where does it go?

- Litter items can be transported across the seas and oceans over long distances by currents and gyres and accumulated in offshore 'garbage patch' areas
- The Great Pacific Garbage Patch is the best known
- It covers an estimated surface area of 1.6 million km² (3 times the size of France)

Watch [The Ocean Cleanup](https://theoceancleanup.com/great-pacific-garbage-patch/) video for more info: [The Great Pacific Garbage Patch Explained](https://theoceancleanup.com/great-pacific-garbage-patch/)

Funded by the European Union

1. North Pacific Gyre, 2. Indian Ocean Gyre, 3. South Pacific Gyre
4. South Atlantic Gyre, 5. North Atlantic Gyre

What type of litter?

Data source (graph): [European Parliament](#), 2018

Funded by the European Union

85% of land-based litter is plastic

Top 10 single-use plastic items

Addressed by the EU Directive 2019/904 on single-use plastics

- Cotton buds
- Cutlery, straws and stirrers
- Balloons and balloon sticks
- Food containers
- Cups for beverages
- Beverage containers
- Cigarette butts
- Plastic bags
- Packets and wrappers
- Wet wipes and sanitary items

Funded by the European Union

Data source: European Commission, 2018
https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/plastics/single-use-plastics_en

W2&W3

Sources of plastics in the environment

Adapted from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/media/infographics/sources-and-pathways-of-plastics/view>

W2&W3

The source

The primary source of marine litter is **mismanagement plastic waste**, which slowly leaks into the environment.

In 2018, it amounted to **3 million tonnes**.

Approximately **80% of marine litter starts on land**, while 20% begins at the sea.

Sources of mismanaged plastic waste

Adapted from EEA, 2023 <https://www.eea.europa.eu/media/infographics/where-does-marine-litter-come-from/view>

W2&W3

How plastics spread to the environment?

Adapted from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/media/infographics/sources-and-pathways-of-plastics/view>

W2&W3

Plastic litter in the sea

WWF (2018). Out of the plastic trap saving the Mediterranean from plastic pollution

W2&W3

Microplastics

What are microplastics and where do they come from?

- Microplastics are tiny pieces of plastic material typically **smaller than 5 mm**
- Originate from degradation of larger plastic objects, such as plastic bags, bottles or fishing nets
- Directly released in the environment as small particles

European Parliament 2018 [Microplastics: sources, effects and solutions](#) accessed Nov. 2023

Based on <https://m-1.theweb.org/environmental-distribution-fate-and-transport/#gsic.tab-0>

W2&W3

Plastics and microplastics

Some numbers in the marine environment

- Plastic waste enters the ocean at a rate of **11 million metric tons per year** (The Pew Charitable Trusts and SYSTEMIQ, 2020)
- Over **200.000 tonnes** of plastic waste enters the Mediterranean Sea every year - a number that is expected to double if significant measures are not taken (IUCN, 2020)
- Recent research estimates that at least **14.4 million tonnes** of microplastics have found its way to the bottom of the world's oceans (Barrett *et al.*, 2020)

Funded by the European Union

EEA, 2021. Plastics, the circular economy and Europe's environment - A priority for action, accessed Nov. 2023

W2&W3

Plastics and microplastics

Impacts on the marine environment

Funded by the European Union

Based on UNEP 2021. Drowning in plastics

W2&W3

FISHERIES CONTRIBUTION TO MARINE LITTER

Marine litter caught in fishing nets

1. Destroys fishing gear
2. Destroys the catch
3. Fishers lose time

€61.7 million/year
Economic loss caused by marine litter to the EU fishing fleet

Funded by the European Union

www.abpcon.eu/news/2018/09-08/great-pacific-garbage-patch-plastic-clean-up-boyan-sta/9714246

W2&W3

Marine litter caught in fishing nets

Economic impacts on the fishing sector

- Floating plastic debris can **affect the engine** cooling systems and become entangled in propellers
(Takehama, 1990; McIlgorm et al., 2011)
- Litter caught in fishing gears can be responsible for **damaging fishing gears, contaminating catch, and even damaging fishing vessels**
(Thomson et al., 2004; Andrady, 2011)
- The total economic cost of this impact has been estimated to be nearly **€61.7 million** in the European Union alone
(Mouat et al., 2010; Acoleyen, 2014)
- The costs of removing litter from fishing nets, damage to catches, repairing gear, entangled propellers and obstructed cooling systems account between **1% and 5%** of fishers' revenue
(FAO, 2018)

W2&W3

LOST FISHING GEAR

W2&W3

Lost fishing gear

Abandoned, lost, or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG)

- ALDFG represent about **10%** of the plastic waste volume present in the oceans
(IUCN, 2021)
- That means somewhere between **500,000 and 1 million tonnes** of fishing gear gets left in the ocean every year
(WWF, 2020)
- Fisheries-related debris is the **largest single category** by volume found in beach litter
(UNEP, 2021)
- ALDFG can continue fishing for years ("ghost fishing") with high impacts on marine ecosystems and consequently on fish stocks. Ghost gear is the **most deadly** form of marine plastic debris
(WWF, 2020)
- EU estimates that about **20%** of the fishing gear used in Europe is dispersed in the Mediterranean Sea, approximately **11,000 tons**
(INTEMARES, 2023)

WWF. 2020. Stop Ghost gear. The most deadly form of marine plastic debris

W2&W3

ALDFG ecological and socioeconomic impacts

<p>Ghost Fishing Derelict gear can continue to capture and kill targeted and vulnerable species, for extended periods</p>	<p>Transfer of Invasive Species Floating derelict gear can travel and spread non-native species to areas where they may harm the ecosystem, economy and human health</p>	<p>Transfer of Toxins Derelict gear can transport and transfer toxins and chemical pollutants into marine food webs</p>	<p>Microplastics Plastic components of derelict gear break down into microplastic pieces, polluting the ocean</p>
<p>Habitat Damage Derelict gear can damage sensitive habitats such as coral reefs, seagrass beds and salt marshes</p>	<p>Obstruction of Navigation Derelict gear can obstruct navigation as well as in-use fishing gear, creating safety risks and equipment damage at sea</p>	<p>Reduced Use Value of Coastal Areas Derelict gear can end up in nearshore habitats, reducing socioeconomic values of recreation, tourism, education and research, and negatively impacting residential and commercial use</p>	

Gilman et al., 2023, Introduction to the Marine Policy special issue on abandoned, lost and discarded fishing gear

W2&W3

GHOST FISHING CYCLE

Adapted from www.bluetubebeach.org/blog/ghost-fishing/

W2&W3

GHOST FISHING EXAMPLES

W2&W3

Causes of lost fishing gear

Direct causes

- Poor weather conditions
- Gear entangled on bottom (rocks)
- Conflict with fishing gear
- Shipwrecks and other artificial wrecks
- Vessel conflict with gear

Indirect causes

- Lack of disposal facilities
- Inaccessibility to disposal facilities
- Differentiated disposal facilities (oils, recycling)
- Expenses of disposal facilities

Adapted from [World Animal Protection](#) (accessed Nov. 2023) and UNEP, 2021.

W2&W3

Lost fishing gear

NetTag project results (2019)

- **Fishing gear more frequently lost:** traps and small pieces of nets
- **Reasons for losing gear:** type of bottom, shipwrecks, adverse weather conditions, bad handling of the gear or interactions with other fishing gear
- **Hotspots for ALDFG:** fishing areas characterised by irregular bottoms (such as rocky bottoms, reefs, wrecks) or high hydrodynamic areas, up to 5-6 NM from the coast
- **Costs of retrieving lost gear:** a trawler vessel can spend between 5000€ to 12000€
- **Financial incentives to recycle fishing gear:** different national/local programs (not well-known by all fishers)

W2&W3

ALDFG reporting and retrieval

Why is important?

- When gear is lost it can often be retrieved if its location is known
- Understanding the extent, locations and causes of gear loss is key to developing effective prevention and mitigation strategies
- The **retrieval of lost gear is the only way to eliminate its negative impacts** (related to navigational safety, habitat or wildlife damage)
- For certain fishing gear like gillnets, prompt retrieval is most effective (delayed retrieval may lead to a loss of structural integrity, reduced fishing capacity, and is less effective in mitigating negative impacts)
- In case of traps and pots, delayed retrievals (conducted days or weeks after loss) can still effectively mitigate significant negative impacts on species

Orinow 2022. Reporting and retrieval of lost fishing gear: recommendations for developing effective programmes

W2&W3

ALDFG | Gillnets

GILLNETS

WWF 2020, Ghost Gear Report
Funded by the European Union

- Gillnets are passive fishing gear, work as a "wall" resting in the water, catching fish that get gilled or entangled
- Highly susceptible to getting lost, often neglected due to its affordability and ease of replacement
- Continues catching fish after being lost, impacting the seabed even as it loses buoyancy
- Recommendations: Implement gear marking, explore alternative materials, and incentivise recovery efforts to minimise its environmental impact

Likelihood of loss					Impact once lost				
1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
				5					5

GGG, 2021, Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

W2&W3

ALDFG | Pots & Traps

POTS & TRAPS

WWF 2020, Ghost Gear Report
Funded by the European Union

- When lost, pots and traps continue attracting animals due to the lingering bait, creating a feedback loop with scavengers preying on trapped animals
- As this fishing gear is usually tied with a buoy, entanglements can still happen after traps/pots are destroyed
- Some countries enforce guidelines or regulations, making it mandatory to implement tracking mechanisms (gear marking or GPS) of devices

Likelihood of loss					Impact once lost				
1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
			4					4	

GGG, 2021, Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

W2&W3

ALDFG | Fish Aggregation Devices

FADs

WWF 2020, Ghost Gear Report
Funded by the European Union

- Often constructed with netting from old purse seines, posing entanglement risks for fish and other animals around the FADs as well as predators that are attracted to the aggregations of prey species
- While many drifting FADs are tracked using satellite buoys, it is common practice to cease tracking drifting FADs, rather than recovering them, when they drift out of fishing areas
- When lost: continued entanglement of vulnerable species in FAD netting and rafts; and harmful impacts to marine and nearshore habitats of beached FADs

Likelihood of loss					Impact once lost				
1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
			3					4	
			5					4	

GGG, 2021, Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

W2&W3

ALDFG | Hooks & Lines

HOOKS & LINES

WWF 2020, Ghost Gear Report
Funded by the European Union

- Often discarded when damaged, as they can be quite cheap
- Longlines can span lengthy distances, but their impact when lost is less than other fishing gear, especially if deployed away from the surface
- However, baited hooks continue to catch fish, creating a feedback loop with larger predators preying on baited fish
- Mainline ropes attached to hooks are made from plastic-derived materials, posing entanglement risks to birds if close to the surface
- Curled turtle-safe hooks help mitigate sea turtle entrapment, reducing this specific impact

Likelihood of loss

Impact once lost

Handline Longline

GGG, 2021, Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

W2&W3

ALDFG | Trawl nets

TRAWL NETS

WWF 2020, Ghost Gear Report
Funded by the European Union

- Expensive and fishers try to avoid losing them
- Often equipped with marking devices for tracking if lost, but entire net loss, necessary for tracking, is rare
- Near seabed trawling, especially in rocky areas, can lead to partial net loss, sinking and moving on the seabed
- Crumpled trawl netting on the seabed has limited chances of catching more fish but may entangle other species like crabs and affect the seabed through smothering
- Surface trawls, usually of polypropylene, can float if torn without weights or catch, having negative impacts similar to FADs

Likelihood of loss

Mid-water Bottom

Impact once lost

Mid-water Bottom

GGG, 2021, Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

W2&W3

ALDFG | Purse seine nets

PURSE SEINE NETS

WWF 2020, Ghost Gear Report
Funded by the European Union

- Segments of nets might unintentionally be lost if left on the working deck -> Dedicated containers for repair sections mitigate this risk
- Large segments of purse seine nets can cause similar harm on the sea surface as FADs and floating trawl segments
- Loss of entire nets is rare and intensive recovery efforts are made for lost nets due to their high economic value and replacement cost
- Lost weighted fishing nets likely sink to the seabed, posing entanglement risks for other animals if mesh size is small
- At the seabed, these nets may impact biodiversity or be moved around by bottom currents once the contained catch is degraded

Likelihood of loss

Impact once lost

GGG, 2021, Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

W2&W3

Bycatch

- Bycatch encompasses **unintentional captures** during fishing operations, extending beyond target species
- **Trawl, longline, and gillnet** have the highest bycatch rates
- **Major threat to marine vulnerable species:** sea turtles, seabirds, elasmobranchs, marine mammals, corals, and sponges
- Also impact fisheries' profitability and sustainability

Funded by the European Union

Medfishcatch, 2022. Understanding and addressing bycatch: key steps for sustainable fisheries

Seabirds

- Seabirds are at risk of entanglement in various fishing gears, including longlines, trawls, and nets
- An estimated 200,000 seabirds suffer accidental fatalities annually in Europe due to interactions with fishing gear
- Seabirds, attracted to bait used by anglers, often fall victim to hooks and entanglement in fishing lines
- Diverse feeding habits, including surface and deep diving, increase the vulnerability of seabirds to fishing gear interactions

BirdLife International | NOAA

Funded by the European Union

Seabird feeding methods: <https://www.gov.uk/en/interactives/5480/seabird-feeding-methods>

How bycatch occurs

BirdLife International: https://youtu.be/o_a3oXbf5x0

W4

Making fisheries safe for seabirds

BirdLife International: https://youtu.be/YGK_1xAZiW0

W4

Gillnet bycatch minimisation measures:

- **'Scary bird device':** Simulates a predator (eagle or falcon) driving birds away from the area of the fishing operation
- **Night settings:** When seabird activity is reduced
- Proper net cleaning and disposal of discards outside of fishing periods: Minimise attraction to birds
- Increased net visibility: Add high-visibility mesh to the top of the net or LED lights
- Increased net depth

Adapted from [SPEA 2021 MedAves Pesca Project](#)

W4

Longline bycatch minimisation measures:

- **'Scary bird device'**: Simulates a predator (eagle or falcon) presence to deter birds
- **'Bird scaring lines' or tori lines**: Colourful streamers, to deter birds from the stern of the vessel
- **Setting of nets/lines at night**: To avoid peak seabird feeding times
- **Weighted Lines**: To increase baited hooks' sink rate, reducing bird snag risk

Trawl bycatch minimisation measures:

- **Tori lines**
- **Night settings**

Adapted from [SPEA 2021 MedAves Pesca Project](#)

W4

Making fisheries safe for seabirds

- Examples of bird-scaring lines or tori lines

Video: <https://vimeo.com/709031744>

Video: <https://youtu.be/szNqpQzETK4?feature=shared>

W4

Sea turtles

- Sea turtles have survived for more than 200 million years
- There are 7 recognised species in the world
- In Europe, turtles are primarily found in the Mediterranean Sea
- Turtles are **migratory** species; they take **20-30 years to mature** and can **live longer than 100 years**
- Turtles have an important role in the ecosystems maintenance and reflect marine environmental health
- 6 out of the 7 are listed as vulnerable, endangered, or critically endangered on the IUCN Red List

-> Nesting populations in the Mediterranean

-> Largest species of turtle
-> Occasional visitor of the Mediterranean and NE Atlantic

Source: [WISE MARINE](#); [MEDASSET](#); [WWF 2022](#)

W4

Sea turtles

- Bycatch poses a significant threat to all species of marine turtles globally, leading to hundreds of thousands of deaths annually
- Turtles are **air-breathers** and can drown if submerged for long, as it can happen when captured by trawl or set nets
- Turtles incidentally captured by longlines are usually released alive, but many will die, mainly for the ingested line
- Simple **onboard best practices** that can reduce the high mortality of captured turtles:
 - Keep any turtle apparently dead or very weak on the deck until they become active again
 - Cut the line very close to the mouth

Funded by the European Union

Source: [EuroTurtles WWF 2022](#)

FAO, 2018 W4

Making fisheries safe for sea turtles

Video: <https://youtu.be/vyhumiEzBqo>

Funded by the European Union

Turtle Excluder Device (TED)

- a grid which diverts marine turtles and other large marine fauna out of a trawl net, already used in tropical shrimp trawls

Source: [WWF 2022](#)

W4

Sharks

Adapted from Artwork by Jamy Silver © Save Our Seas Foundation

WHY ARE SHARKS IMPORTANT?

Across the world's oceans, there are over **500 species** of shark.

They have inhabited our oceans for over **400 million years**.

Some are **top predators**, others are the **clean-up crew** of the ocean.

Their diverse roles are part of a balance needed for **healthy oceans**.

save our seas foundation

Species shown: Goblin shark, Whale shark, Zebra shark, Tiger shark, Angel shark, Catshark, Blue shark, Basking shark, Epaulletie shark, Scalloped hammerhead, Bonnethead.

W4

Sharks

Adapted from: Artwork by Jaimy Silver © Save Our Seas Foundation

WHY ARE SHARKS IMPORTANT?

Losing sharks can disrupt the **delicate ecosystem balance** that they help maintain.

As many as **100 million** sharks may be killed every year in commercial fisheries.

Many shark populations have **declined by more than 90%** due to overfishing, climate change and habitat loss.

Our future depends on the oceans. The ripple effects of an ocean without sharks are complex and potentially devastating.

save our seas foundation

Marine mammals

- Marine mammals play crucial ecological roles and are indicators of marine ecosystem health
- They are generally **highly mobile**, possess **large body sizes**, and have **low reproductive rates**
- Which makes them **vulnerable** to human-related stressors
- The disappearance of large predators (e.g. dolphins) has a wider impact on the environment and marine resources
- Bycatch/entanglement in fishing gear poses the **greatest threat** to marine mammal species globally
- Although it's **illegal** to catch marine mammals
- Over 600,000 marine mammals are accidentally captured each year worldwide

BOTTLENOSE DOLPHIN © M. Camm

LONG-FINNED PILOT WHALE © M. Camm

GRAY SEAL NOAA Fisheries

Funded by the European Union

Source: [FAO CETAMBICTION project](#)

Marine mammals

Why bycatch happens?

- Same fishing area or target species (trophic competition)
- Attracting dolphins near fishing boats (depredation)
- Lack of visibility/selectivity of some fishing gear that accidentally catches non-target animals

WDC

Gillnets Purse Seine Trawl

Funded by the European Union

© richardpalmirgraphics.com

Marine mammals bycatch mitigation

- Improving the visibility of fishing gear
 - ✓ Active or passive acoustic deterrents
 - ✓ Acoustic reflectors
 - ✓ Informative warning signal (DOLPHINFREE project)
 - ✓ Change of net colour
 - ✓ Lighting of nets
- Modification of fishing gear
 - ✓ Modification of the nets
 - ✓ Trawl exclusion system
 - ✓ "Intelligent" fishing gear
- Changes in fishing practices
 - ✓ Alternative fishing gear
 - ✓ Duration and period of immersion of the fishing gear
 - ✓ Depth of the net (2-4m below surface)
 - ✓ Adoption of good practice
- Fishing effort limitation and management
 - ✓ Time and space closure
 - ✓ Area closure based on reaching a catch limit
 - ✓ "Move-on" rule
 - ✓ Predictive fisheries management
- Regulatory and incentive measures
 - ✓ Regulation, Monitoring and surveillance
 - ✓ Economic levers

Source: CETAMBICION project

W4

Acoustic Deterrent Devices - 'pingers'

Excluder Device

W4

Backdown procedure

Source: UNEP/CMS & WWF, 2020. Guidelines for the safe and humane handling and release of bycaught small cetaceans from fishing gear.

W4

FISHING GEAR INNOVATIONS DESIGNED TO LOWER THE RISK OF ENTANGLEMENT FOR LARGE WHALES

DEPLOY FISHING GEAR MADE OF COMPONENTS WITH A LOW BREAKING STRENGTH
The use of polyethylenes, time-tension line cutters or plastic links, for example, offers a breaking strength of 770 kg or less, which makes it easier to release an entangled animal

USE A MAXIMUM ROPE DIAMETER OF 16 mm
Too large a diameter increases the breaking strength and complicates the release of an entangled animal, while excessively thin rope (6 mm) can lead to more severe skin injuries

USE ROPELESS GEAR
Technologies include various types of remote triggering devices and GPS positioning and recovery systems in order to eliminate the need for vertical lines

REDUCE FLOATING ROPE ON WATER SURFACE
Adopt good fishing practices to reduce floating rope such as rope shot, inflatable lift bag or simply properly coiling one's rope

USE SINKING ROPE BETWEEN TRAPS OR POTS
Sinking rope helps limit the amount of rope floating above the seafloor

AVOID USING SINGLE-POT GEAR
Traps or pots can be deployed in series to reduce the number of buoys and the amount of rope used

Adapted from: <https://navigationbalesmes.ca/en/what-you-can-do/>

Safe handling and release

- Maximises survival chances of bycatch species after interaction with fishing gear
- Includes best practice methods and vessel manoeuvres to avoid taking bycatch species
- In purse seine operations, bycatch can be released from the net whilst in the water or released once brought on deck
- With line fishing operations bycatch may either be released from the side of the vessel or after being brought on board
- There are safe handling and release guides for different species and fishing gear

Source: RMIS

Funded by the European Union

ACTIONS TO REDUCE PLASTIC POLLUTION FROM FISHERIES

Tackling sea-based marine litter sources

EU actions

- **EU Directive 2019/883** on **port reception facilities** to tackle sea-based marine litter
- **EU Directive 2019/904** on **single use plastic** products and **fishing gear** containing plastic
- One of the six main interim targets of the **Zero Pollution Action Plan** for 2030 is **reducing litter at sea by 50%**
- Council Regulation (EC) No 1224/2009 requires Union fishing vessels to have the equipment on board to **retrieve lost gear**

DG MARE 3018 Lost fishing gear - a trap for our ocean (info@ec.europa.eu)

W2&W3, W5

Directive 2019/883 on Port Reception Facilities

EU Directive for the delivery of waste from ships

- Aims to protect the marine environment by reducing discharges of waste from ships, and to improve efficiency of maritime operations in ports; ensuring that more waste is delivered on shore, in particular garbage, including waste from the fishing sector such as derelict fishing gear
- **100% INDIRECT FEE OBLIGATION** – allows the **FREE delivery of all litter** (including fishing gears and passively fished litter), up to the maximum dedicated storage capacity of the boat
- **GREEN-SHIP rebate** - fishing vessels should be encouraged to undertake certain measures (waste prevention and on-board waste management) to be eligible for a green-ship rebate

W2&W3, W5

Potential use of eco-friendly materials

Preventing plastic from ending up in the ocean in the first place!

- Current development of **biodegradable nets and line** -> reducing ghost fishing and microplastics
- Maintaining strength and durability for a few months and degrades in water

<https://www.ocean.com/pages/sustainable-fishing>

<https://www.brainiac.com/en/boats/using-green-commercial-fishing>

W5

Tackling sea-based marine litter sources

Fishers are part of the solution!

- Delivery of waste to port reception facilities, including fishing gear waste
- Collecting and bringing passively fished waste ashore
- Retrieving or reporting lost fishing gear
- Recycling end-of-life fishing gear
- Participation on Clean-up Initiatives; Fishing for Litter

© NetTag project, Clean Ocean Day

Funded by the European Union

W2&W3, W5

Tackling sea-based marine litter sources

Fishers are part of the solution!

- All fishers have a bag or trash bin on board
- All boats have space on board to bring the waste produced back to land

Funded by the European Union

W2&W3, W5

How to reduce plastic waste?

Individual actions

use your own bottle

avoid unnecessary packaging

opt for fully recyclable packaging

prevention is key!

bring your own lunch box

dispose of plastic recycling correctly

pick up litter & participate in beach clean-ups

Funded by the European Union

Based on EUEIC and Safety4Sea

W2&W3, W5

Greenhouse gases (GHG)

What are GHG and how do fisheries contribute to them?

- Human activities, including fisheries, produce GHG through the consumption fossil fuel
- GHG is a group of gases contributing to global warming and climate change (carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide and fluorinated gases)
- GHG trap heat from the sun to keep surface warm while some heat is released back into space

NOAA
Funded by the European Union

GHG effects on the ocean

1. Ocean acidification

- shelled organisms (e.g. oysters, clams, sea urchins) have difficulties building and maintaining shells
- jeopardises this food source and the larger food web

2. Sea level rise

- as the ocean warms, the volume of water increases
- coasts at risk from erosion and high-tide flooding

3. Warmer temperatures melting sea ice (contributing to sea level rise)

- glaciers are shrinking
- the Arctic is warming most rapidly compared to global average

NOAA 2021
Funded by the European Union

Net Zero emissions by 2050

Fisheries and aquaculture sectors

- Under the Green Deal, Europe has committed to become the first **climate-neutral** continent by **2050** and to **cut the GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030** (compared to 1990)
- This means a **reduction of 30% by 2030** (compared to 2005) in the **fishing sector**
- To reach a neutral CO₂ footprint, all sectors must play their part in **emitting less** and **protecting natural ecosystems**, such as the ocean, so they absorb more carbon
- The European Commission proposed **measures to accelerate energy transition**, focusing on fuel efficiency and renewable, low-carbon power sources (COM(2023) 100 final)

EC 2023 COM(2023) 100

Funded by the European Union

Climate-smart management requirements

Cut fossil fuel emissions

FUEL SAVINGS

- 50% can be achieved by optimising fishing vessel structures, gears, and routes
- 100% from switching to renewable energy fuels & propulsion

The EU's energy transition initiative of its fisheries must transform the sector to one of low-impact

Prioritise moving away from the most fuel-intensive and high impact fishing – such as bottom trawling – towards:

- Fuel efficient practices
- Selective, low-impact gears
- Green energy sources

Adapted OCEANA 2023 [Fighting the climate crisis requires climate-smart fishing in Europe](#) w5

Climate-smart management requirements

Rebuild and maintain fish biomass

Follow scientific advice and end overfishing

Adopt an ecosystem-based approach to fisheries management

Allocate fishing opportunities to prioritise low-impact, less fuel-intensive fleets

This approach has multiple benefits:

- 1 Protect the role of fish in the carbon cycle
- 2 More fish abundance reduces fuel & operational costs
- 3 Decreases fleet's fuel footprint per kg of seafood

Adapted OCEANA 2023 [Fighting the climate crisis requires climate-smart fishing in Europe](#) w5

Strategies to reduce GHG emissions

- Fuel loads per catch can range based on gear, vessel, catch, and more
 - Slowing down during steaming (reduce fuel use whenever possible)
 - Investing in technological innovations for vessels
 - Remaining adaptable and resilient as the industry evolves

EPRS, 2023 [Decarbonising the fishing sector](#)

W5

Let's clean up the ocean together!

Thank you for your attention

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

www.nettagplus.eu

Follow @NetTagProject

Annex 11. Proposed agenda for Workshop #2

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

2nd WORKSHOP Marine litter produced on board

Agenda

Place | Date | Time

13:45 - 14:00	Registration
14:00 - 14:10	Welcome
14:10 - 14:30	Exercise 1: Litter classification
14:30 - 14:50	Exercise 2: Litter destination
14:50 - 15:10	Presentation of results & discussion
15:10 - 15:30	Exercise 3: Further actions and dissemination
15:30 - 15:50	Presentation of results & discussion
15:50 - 16:00	Workshop final conclusions
16:00 - 16:20	Coffee break

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Annex 12. Support material for the Workshop #2

PLASTIC BAG

PLASTIC BOTTLE

YOGURT PACKAGING

ALUMINUM FOOD CONTAINER

PLASTIC FOOD PACKAGE

FOOD CONTAINER

FRUIT WASTE

CAN

GLASS BOTTLE

TOILET PAPER

FACIAL TISSUE

ALUMINUM FOIL

PLASTIC GLOVES

RUBBER BOOTS

CIGARETTE BUTTS

CONTAINER

PLASTIC BOXES

STYROFOAM BOXES

SCRAP METAL

BROKEN SMARTPHONE

BROKEN TELEVISION

OLD TIRES

WOOD

ROPE

FISHING NETS

FISHING POTS & TRAPS

FISHING NET FLOATS

FISHING MATERIAL

STARFISH

MACROALGAE

SEABIRDS

DOLPHINS

SEA TURTLES

Annex 13. Exercise sheets for the Workshop #2

Exercise 1: Classify each item as litter or non-litter

LITTER	
NON-LITTER	

Exercise 1 | Group -----
Workshop #2 'Marine litter produced on board' | *add the location of the workshop* . (dd/ mm/ yyyy)

Exercise 2A: Based on your own experience, identify the destination of each litter item

THROW OVERBOARD

BRING TO SHORE

Exercise 2A | Group -----
Workshop #2 'Marine litter produced on board' | *add the location of the workshop* . [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Exercise 2B: Based on your own experience, identify the destination of each litter item that is brought to shore

STAYS ON PORT	GENERAL GARBAGE CONTAINER	RECYCLING

Exercise 2B | Group -----
Workshop #2 'Marine litter produced on board' | *add the location of the workshop* | [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Exercise 3A: Write suggestions to reduce and manage marine litter produced on board

SUGGESTIONS

to reduce marine litter produced on board, best practices to implement (on board and at ports)

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS (what you're good at)

WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)

OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)

THREATS (risks or challenges)

Annex 14. Proposed agenda for Workshop #3

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

3rd WORKSHOP

Marine litter collected by fishing gear

Agenda

Place | Date | Time

13:45 - 14:00	Registration
14:00 - 14:10	Welcome
14:10 - 14:30	Exercise 1: Litter passively caught in fishing nets
14:30 - 14:50	Exercise 2: Destination of litter caught in fishing nets
14:50 - 15:10	Presentation of results & discussion
15:10 - 15:30	Exercise 3: Further actions and dissemination
15:30 - 15:50	Presentation of results & discussion
15:50 - 16:00	Workshop final conclusions
16:00 - 16:20	Coffee break

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Annex 15. Exercise sheets for the Workshop #3

Exercise 1: Based on your own experience, register the litter items commonly caught in your fishing nets

OTHER	
FISHERIES DEBRIS	
DOMESTIC LITTER	

Exercise 1 | Group -----
Workshop #3 'Marine litter collected by fishing gears' | **add the location of the workshop** . [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Exercise 2A: Based on your own experience, register the litter items caught in your fishing nets that are thrown overboard and the ones brought to shore

THROW OVERBOARD

BRING TO SHORE

Exercise 2A | Group -----
Workshop #3 'Marine litter collected by fishing gears' | *ladd the location of the workshop* | . [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Exercise 2B: Based on your own experience, register the destination of each litter item (capture in fishing nets) that is brought to shore

STAYS ON PORT	GENERAL GARBAGE CONTAINER	RECYCLING

Exercise 2B | Group -----
Workshop #3 'Marine litter collected by fishing gears' | *add the location of the workshop* | . [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Exercise 3A: Write suggestions to motivate fishers to become Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

SUGGESTIONS

suggest measures (on board and at ports) to encourage the collection and proper management of marine litter, during normal fishing activities

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS (what you're good at)

WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)

OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)

THREATS (risks or challenges)

Exercise 3B: Write suggestions to disseminate information and encourage other fishers to become Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

SPREAD THE WORD

suggest ways of getting other fishers involved

LEADERSHIP

identify either individual fishers, vessels or communities that demonstrate leadership and social influence

CITIZENS' SCIENCE

DO YOU KNOW ANY MARINE LITTER PLATFORM?

YES NO IF YES, WHICH? -----

ARE YOU WILLING TO JOIN A MARINE LITTER PLATFORM?

YES NO MAYBE

WHAT TYPE OF DATA?

IN WHAT CONDITIONS?

Annex 16. Proposed agenda for Workshop #4

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

4th WORKSHOP

Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation

Agenda

Place | Date | Time

13:45 - 14:00	Registration
14:00 - 14:10	Welcome
14:10 - 14:30	Exercise 1: Species commonly captured
14:30 - 14:50	Exercise 2: Best practices to reduce bycatch
14:50 - 15:10	Exercise 3: Protocols in case of bycatch
15:10 - 15:30	Exercise 4: Dissemination and leadership
15:30 - 15:50	Presentation of results & discussion
15:50 - 16:00	Workshop final conclusions
16:00 - 16:20	Coffee break

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Annex 17. Support material for the Workshop #4

SEABIRDS

MARINE MAMMALS

SHARKS

SEA TURTLES

SPONGES

CORALS

Annex 18. Exercise sheets for the Workshop #4

Exercise 1: Based on your experience, register the species commonly involved in bycatch, link them to the fishing gears, identify the endangered species.

BYCATCH SPECIES PER FISHING GEAR

BYCATCH SPECIES:	FISHING GEAR:

more captured
less captured

ENDANGERED SPECIES

Exercise 1 | Group _____
 Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | **add the location of the workshop** |
 [dd/mm/yyyy]

Exercise 2: Based on your experience, which measures can you adopt to reduce bycatch?

MINIMISATION MEASURES

MEASURES TO REDUCE BYCATCH

- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____

HOW TO IMPLEMENT THE SELECTED MEASURES?

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS (what you're good at)

WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)

OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)

THREATS (risks or challenges)

Exercise 2 | Group _____
 Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | **add the location of the workshop** |
 (dd/ mm/ yy)

Exercise 3: Based on your experience, how do you handle bycatch and which protocols /best practices can you adopt in case of bycatch?

BEST PRACTICES/ PROTOCOLS

COMMON PRACTICES IN CASE OF BYCATCH:

NOTIFICATION (competent authorities, other):

ARE THERE IMPLEMENTED PROTOCOLS?

YES NO IF YES, WHICH?

SUGGESTIONS:

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS (what you're good at)

WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)

OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)

THREATS (risks or challenges)

Exercise 3 | Group -----
 Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | **add the location of the workshop** |
 (dd/ mm/ yy)

Exercise 4: Write suggestions to disseminate information and encourage other fishers to adopt similar practices.

SPREAD THE WORD

suggest ways of disseminating best practices to fellow fishers

LEADERSHIP

identify either individual fishers, vessels or communities that demonstrate leadership and social influence

Exercise 4 | Group
Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation' | *add the location of the workshop*
(dd/ mm/ yy)

Annex 19. Support material to discuss best practices to reduce bycatch (Workshop #4)

This annex provides a comprehensive list of potential measures aimed at minimising bycatch. Partners should select the most relevant measures for discussion with fishers according to local specificities.

GEAR AND BEST PRACTICES	FISHERIES TYPE						BYCATCH SPECIES			
	Gillnets	Longlines	Pots/ Traps	Trawls	Purse Seine	Marine mammals	Sea turtles	Sharks and rays	Seabirds	
<p>Acoustic Pingers</p> <p>Acoustic pingers serve as a marine mammal deterrent device in net fisheries by emitting a sound that can be detected within a certain distance of the net. Implementation of acoustic pingers in gillnet fisheries has become widespread over the last decade, especially in the northern Atlantic, where it is required by law in numerous fisheries.</p>	✓									
<p>Avoid Hotspots</p> <p>Hotspots are areas that have a higher abundance of bycatch taxa where it is more likely to have high bycatch rates if fishing is conducted. It is a best practice to avoid setting fishing gear in these locations.</p>	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
<p>Backdown Method</p> <p>The backdown method is conducted after setting the purse seine net but before finishing the haul. This process creates a channel and an opening at the back of the net where non-target species (especially small cetaceans and sea turtles) can escape at the surface.</p>					✓		✓			
<p>Bird scaring devices</p> <p>Shaped like a small eagle or hawk, the kite simulates the presence of a predator, driving the birds away from the fishing area. To maximise its effectiveness, it should be combined with other measures.</p>	✓	✓		✓				✓		
<p>Circle Hooks</p> <p>In circle hooks, the pointed tip is bent back towards the shaft decreasing the spacing between the sharpened tip and shaft and changing the hook angle. The shape of the circle hook makes it harder for ETP bycatch to get hooked due to differences in jaw morphologies, but doesn't impact catch rates in fish and can even in some cases increase catch rates.</p>									✓	

1/5

Exercise 2 support material: Examples of bycatch solutions
Workshop #4 'Sustainable practices: bycatch reduction and marine conservation'

GEAR AND BEST PRACTICES		FISHERIES TYPE								BYCATCH SPECIES				
		Gillnets	Longlines	Pots/ Traps	Trawls	Purse Seine	Marine mammals	Sea turtles	Sharks and rays	Seabirds				
Decreased Soak Times	Soak time is the amount of time that deployed fishing gear stays in the water. The longer the gear is set in the water, the higher the bycatch rate will be.	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Excluder Devices	Excluder devices are modifications to trawl nets that block specific taxa from getting dragged into the cod end of the net and allows them to swim out while the trawl net is being towed. Excluder devices are effective and being used in trawl fisheries that interact with bottlenose dolphins, common dolphins, seals, and turtles, for example.				✓				✓					
Hook Shielding Devices	A hook shielding device encases or covers the tip of the baited hook during the longline set to prevent predation by seabirds. The shielding devices is designed to then open or release the hook at a specified depth below which seabirds can dive.		✓										✓	
Jelly FAD	Jelly FADs are non-entangling biodegradable fish aggregating devices that have proven to be just as effective as traditional FADs at aggregating targeted fish species. Due to their structure design and materials used, they do not pose an entanglement risk to sea turtles, dolphins/porpoises, and sharks/rays, and if lost will biodegrade much faster than traditional FADs.							✓		✓			✓	
Management of offal and discards	Birds are attracted to fishing vessels to feed on processing waste and discarded fish. To reduce this attraction, effective waste management is crucial: i) retain waste onboard during trips. If impracticable, avoid discharge during fishing activity; ii) where retention of waste is impracticable, convert offal into fish meal and restrict discharge to liquid only; iii) where meal production and		✓											✓

GEAR AND BEST PRACTICES	FISHERIES TYPE								BYCATCH SPECIES					
	Gillnets	Longlines	Pots/ Traps	Trawls	Purse Seine	Marine mammals	Sea turtles	Sharks and rays	Seabirds					
retention are impracticable, temporally store waste for at least two hours before controlled discharge it in batches; iv) if other methods aren't feasible, reduce waste to smaller particles. Efforts should be made to eliminate or limit ofal discharge during active fishing periods.														
Modified Purse Seine					✓								✓	
Net Lights	✓								✓					
Night Settings	✓	✓											✓	
Non-Dolphin/Whale Shark Sets										✓				
Non-Entangling Biodegradable FAD													✓	✓

GEAR AND BEST PRACTICES	FISHERIES TYPE							BYCATCH SPECIES			
	Gillnets	Longlines	Pots/ Traps	Trawls	Purse Seine	Marine mammals	Sea turtles	Sharks and rays	Seabirds		
structure and hang in the water often entangle non-target species such as sea turtles, seabirds, and sharks that are also attracted to the FAD.											
Non-Steel Leaders Leaders are a segment of the branch line that the baited hook is directly attached to. For fisheries that do not retain sharks, it is recommended to use a leader material that can be cut, allowing sharks to break off in the water, or be cut from the main line by the crew when hauling.	✓							✓			
Ropeless (On-Demand) Pot/Trap Systems Ropeless (On-Demand) pot/trap systems are designed to be deployed without surface buoy lines in the water column and therefore nearly entirely reduce the risk of entanglement for ETP species. Most of these systems utilise an acoustic release device that can be activated from the boat which will either release a buoy line or inflate a float bag attached to the pots/traps in the water. The pots/traps can then be retrieved by fishers.			✓								
Sharkguard Longline fisheries set out a long main line with hundreds to thousands of baited hooks attached on branch lines. Sharks and rays are attracted to baited hooks in addition to target species resulting in tens of millions caught as bycatch in longline fisheries each year.		✓						✓			
Smart Buoys Smart buoys provide constant location information so that gear can be tracked remotely, which helps fishers locate gear if it has come loose or moved in a storm. Importantly, it also can alert fishers when buoy lines are being dragged, for example provide continuous real-time location data of entangled whales which would greatly increase disentanglement success.	✓		✓					✓	✓		

GEAR AND BEST PRACTICES		FISHERIES TYPE							BYCATCH SPECIES			
		Gillnets	Longlines	Pots/Traps	Trawls	Purse Seine	Marine mammals	Sea turtles	Sharks and rays	Seabirds		
Streamer (tori) lines	Streamer lines, also called tori or bird scaring lines, deter birds from sinking baits, dramatically reducing seabird attacks and related mortalities. Runs from a high point at the stern to a device or mechanism that creates drag at its terminus. Brightly coloured streamers hanging from the aerial extent of the line scare birds from flying to and under the line, preventing them from reaching the baited hooks, becoming hooked and subsequently killed.		✓		✓					✓		
Sub-Surface Sets	Surface set gillnets can catch sea turtles and small cetaceans that spend most of their time at the surface. By increasing the depth of the float line (the top rope on the net) a few meters, sea turtles and small cetaceans at the surface can pass over without becoming entangled, decreasing the bycatch rate.	✓							✓			
Weak Inserts, Weak Rope	Pots and traps fisheries use buoy lines (high-strength ropes) attached to pots and traps to mark gear on the ocean bottom. Buoy lines that extend from the trap on the seafloor to the surface sometimes cause marine mammals and sea turtles to become entangled often leading to severe injury or death.							✓				
Weighted Branchline	Weighted branch lines increase the sink rate of baited hooks decreasing the amount of time that they can be predated on by seabirds and that seabirds can get hooked.	✓										✓

Source of data: Bycatch Solutions Hub (<https://bycatchsolutions.org/solutions/?keyword=&active-filter=ocean&ocean=northern-atlantic-ocean>); Bycatch Management Information System (<https://www.bmis-bycatch.org/mitigation-techniques>); FAO (Marine mammal bycatch mitigation, <https://www.fao.org/fishery/en/bycatch-mitigation-mammals/search>); ACAP (<https://www.acap.org/bycatch-mitigation/mitigation-advice>); SPEA (https://www.spea.pt/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Factsheetsx3_FINAL.pdf)

Source of fishing gear and species icons: Bycatch Solutions Hub (<https://bycatchsolutions.org/solutions/?keyword=&active-filter=ocean&ocean=northern-atlantic-ocean>)

Annex 20. Proposed agenda for Workshop #5

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

5th WORKSHOP Reducing fisheries footprint

Agenda

Place | Date | Time

13:45 - 14:00	Registration
14:00 - 14:10	Welcome
14:10 - 14:30	Exercise 1: Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions
14:30 - 14:50	Exercise 2: Use of alternative/eco-friendly materials
14:50 - 15:10	Exercise 3: Dissemination and leadership
15:10 - 15:30	Presentation of results & discussion
15:30 - 15:40	Workshop final conclusions
15:40 - 16:00	Coffee break

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Annex 21. Support material to discuss the reduction of GHG emissions (Workshop #5)

REDUCTION OF GHG EMISSIONS

Flying trawl doors to reduce the drag on the bottom and improve fuel consumption

Vessel that runs on solar power

Hybrid (diesel-electric) fishing vessel

OPTIMISE VESSELS:

- ✓ Fuel optimised hull design
- ✓ Drag force reduction including hull cleaning and treatment
- ✓ Optimise operations
- ✓ Improved engine (propulsion and auxiliary engines)
- ✓ Optimise freezing systems on factory vessels
- ✓ Consumption monitoring system to optimise RPM, propeller power, etc.

OPTIMISE GEAR:

- ✓ Drag force reduction and improved catchability

USE CLEANEST DIESEL

FISHING BEHAVIOUR:

- ✓ Planning of fishing activities (when and where to fish)
- ✓ Reduce or optimise speed
- ✓ Energy audits and crew training

ALTERNATIVE ENERGY:

- ✓ Liquefied Natural/Fossil Gas (LNG/LFG)
- ✓ Hybrid (fossil/electric)
- ✓ Sail assisted propulsion and wave energy
- ✓ Full electrification
- ✓ Methanol
- ✓ Biofuels (biogas, biodiesel)
- ✓ Hydrogen
- ✓ Ammonia

CATCH USE:

- ✓ Full utilization of catch and trimmings

NEW VESSELS:

- ✓ Replace old vessels with more energy-efficient ones

Exercise 1 support material

Workshop #5 'Reducing fisheries footprint' | [Add the location of the workshop](#) . [dd/mm/yyyy]

Annex 22. Exercise sheets for the Workshop #5

Exercise 1: Based on your experience, which measures can you adopt to reduce greenhouse gas emissions? How to implement them?

ENERGY TRANSITION

MEASURES TO REDUCE GHG EMISSIONS

- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____
- ✓ _____

HOW TO IMPLEMENT THE SELECTED MEASURES?

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS (what you're good at)

WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)

OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)

THREATS (risks or challenges)

Exercise 1 | Group _____
Workshop #5 'Reducing fisheries footprint' | *add the location of the workshop* | [dd/ mm/ yyyy]

Exercise 2: Based on your experience, which materials can be replaced to reduce fishers' reliance on plastics? How to implement them?

ECO-FRIENDLY MATERIALS

WHICH MATERIALS CAN BE REPLACED?

- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓

HOW TO IMPLEMENT THIS MEASURES?

SWOT ANALYSIS

STRENGTHS (what you're good at)

WEAKNESSES (areas to improve)

OPPORTUNITIES (chances for positive development)

THREATS (risks or challenges)

Exercise 2 | Group -----
 Workshop #5 'Reducing fisheries footprint' | **add the location of the workshop** | .ddd/ mm/ yyyy

Exercise 3: Write suggestions to disseminate information and encourage other fishers to adopt similar practices.

SPREAD THE WORD

suggest ways of disseminating best practices to fellow fishers

LEADERSHIP

identify either individual fishers, vessels or communities that demonstrate leadership and social influence

Exercise 3 | Group _____
Workshop #5 'Reducing fisheries footprint' | **add the location of the workshop** | .ddd/ mm/ yyyy

Annex 23. Support material to discuss the use of more eco-friendly materials (Workshop #5)

WHICH MATERIALS CAN BE REPLACED TO REDUCE THE USE OF PLASTIC?

- ✓ Fishing nets
- ✓ Floats
- ✓ Cleaning products
- ✓ Cleaning practices
- ✓ Cleaning products
- ✓ Cleaning practices
- ✓ Cleaning practices
- ✓ Clothing . . .
- ✓ Lines and ropes
- ✓ Bait containers
- ✓ Storage solutions
- ✓ Packages
- ✓ Buoy
- ✓ Pots and traps
- ✓ Fishing Lures

Exercise 2 support material
 Workshop #5: Sustainable practices: reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and use of alternative/eco-friendly materials | **add the location of the workshop** | . /dd/ mm/ yy/

Annex 24. Proposed agenda for Workshop #6

NETTAG+ Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

6th WORKSHOP NETTAG+ solutions

Agenda

Place | Date | Time

13:45 - 14:00	Registration
14:00 - 14:30	Welcome & Talk on the NETTAG+ solutions
14:30 - 14:40	Exercise 1: General evaluation of the NETTAG+ solutions
14:40 - 15:00	Exercise 2: Discussion of the NETTAG+ solutions
15:00 - 15:20	Presentation of results & discussion
15:20 - 15:30	Workshop final conclusions
15:30 - 15:50	Coffee break

Annex 25. Poster for the Workshop #6

<p>MITIGATE</p>				
<p>AVOID</p>				
<p>PREVENT</p>				
				<p>Exercise 1. Evaluate each NETTAG+ solution by placing a colored sticker (green, yellow or red) in each box Workshop #6 'NETTAG+ solutions' <i>add the location of the workshop</i> <i>ddd/mm/yyyy</i></p>

Annex 26. Exercise sheets for the Workshop #6

 PREVENT	ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES	SUGGESTIONS / UPGRADES
	AWARENESS ACTIONS > > > > > >	> > > > > >	> > > > > >
PORT FACILITIES & PLANS > > > > > >	> > > > > >	> > > > > >	> > > > > >
FISHERS REWARD PROGRAM > > > > > >	> > > > > >	> > > > > >	> > > > > >

Exercise 2A | Group -----
 Workshop #6 'NETTAG+ solutions' | *[add the location of the workshop] . [dd/mm/yyyy]*

AVOID

ADVANTAGES

DISADVANTAGES

SUGGESTIONS / UPGRADES

ACOUSTIC TAGS

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

Exercise 2B | Group _____
 Workshop #6 'NETTAG+ solutions' | *add the location of the workshop* . [dd/mm/yyyy]

ADVANTAGES

DISADVANTAGES

SUGGESTIONS / UPGRADES

DETECTION OF LOST GEARS

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

MAPPING ROBOT

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

✓

Exercise 2C | Group _____
 Workshop #6 'NETTAG+ solutions' | *add the location of the workshop* . [dd/mm/yyyy]

